

Session D

**ENVIRONMENT
PROTECTION AND
NATURAL RESOURCES
MANAGEMENT**

DENDROLOGICAL ASPECTS OF VEGETATIVE REPRODUCTION OF SOME WALNUT GENOTYPES

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Walnut (*Juglans regia* L.) is the most widespread tree nut in the world. There is a great diversity of genotypes differing in forestry, productivity, physical and chemical nut traits. Using a range of methodologies, from morphological markers to the most recent advances in genome analysis, many genetic studies of walnut have been conducted during the past years, including examination of diversity, determination of relationships within or among germplasm collections and populations, phylogenetic and origin elucidation, genetic map construction, and biotic or abiotic stress investigations. The genetic improvement of walnut has undergone great evolution. Some of them have been evaluated as promising and may serve as germplasm sources for breeding. Germplasm diversity is commonly evaluated with the help of morphological descriptors. This is usually the first step in classifying and describing germplasm and in studying heritability of traits for a new breeding program and selection of superior genotypes.

Cultivated walnut varieties, generally well adapted to climatic conditions of the different production zones, often lack some important agronomic characteristics. It would therefore be useful to select in natural populations or create through hybridization new cultivars combining characters of improved climate adaptation, early fruiting, high productivity, disease tolerance and quality fruit production. This is possible given the very large and so far unexploited variability within the *Juglans regia* L. species. Long juvenility period and high variation between trees in terms of different characteristics, usually make it impossible to establish uniform orchards. Yield and quality of fruit and kernel is low and could not compete with the production of the countries that have used the cultivars. So, breeding and introducing of new suitable walnut cultivars is necessary for walnut development. However, both the common walnut *Juglans regia* and black walnut *J. nigra* are quite particular in terms of optimal growing conditions. Hybrid walnuts provide an exciting alternative. It is possible to encourage and control hybridisation through tree breeding programmes. Hybrid species tend to have greater than either of their parents, and may be more tolerant to a wider range of conditions.

Root systems have a strong influence on the vigor of the tree. Vigorous rootstocks are commonly used to increase productivity or to decrease it. This feature is especially important when dealing with trees, as most of the research in breeding with walnuts has been looking for very vigorous scions that must be grafted on seedling rootstocks of unknown and heterogeneous growth capabilities. Once selected scions are shown to be very vigorous and productive on their own roots, it can be assumed that micropropagated selections of walnuts must result in more homogeneous and vigorous trees than the same selections grafted onto seedling rootstocks.

Plant breeding has always impacted food production and played a vital role in improving human nutrition. However, this has also increased uniformity within the world's agricultural crops, contributing to increased genetic vulnerability to biotic and abiotic stresses. For these reasons, it is important to understand better the impacts of modern plant breeding on genetic diversity. In the same way, intelligent management of this diversity could be of valuable assistance to breeders.

Key words: *Juglans regia* L., vegetative reproduction, cultivated varieties, breeding, introducing.

GROUNDWATER CHEMISTRY OF SARMATIAN AQUIFERS IN RABNITA AND DUBASARI DISTRICTS

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In Rabnita and Dubasari districts the aquifers in the strata of Neogene age are used for the water supplies of the local population. The strata are represented by limestones, and in some areas and levels by marls and clays. Regionally, these strata belong to the Lower and Middle Sarmatian stage of Middle and Upper Miocene. In most cases there are no waterproof strata between Lower and Middle Sarmatian limestones, and the rocks of both sub-horizons represent a single, united aquifer. The limestones of Lower and Middle Sarmatian often are almost identical lithologically, and the limit between them is identified only by fauna. In Rabnita district the rocks of Lower Sarmatian are uncovered by the erosion of the River Dniester, and the Middle Sarmatian limestones lie above the level of erosion. Thus, the Middle Sarmatian is drained by water springs and the principal water horizon is located in the rocks of Lower Sarmatian only. In Dubasari district the Lower Sarmatian strata lie below the level of Dniester waters; they show low transmissivity, and these waters are not used exclusively for the supply of population. The principal water horizon is Middle Sarmatian only. The most wells in the district were drilled down until the limit of Lower Sarmatian or even Upper Badenian aquifers, but pump mostly the waters of Middle Sarmatian. There are no waterproof strata between the two Sarmatian horizons, but Middle Sarmatian waters dominate because of higher transmissivity values of the Middle Sarmatian limestones. In Rabnita district there are many wells in and around the district centre proper (Rabnita, Smalena, Harjau). The chemical composition of Lower Sarmatian groundwaters is mixed. The dominating anion is HCO_3^- , with about 40-60%, the second is SO_4^{2-} , with about 25-40%, Cl almost never exceeds 20%. Among the cations, all 3 are presented above 20%, in the majority of wells Na is first, sometimes Ca or Mg. In Varancau, the chemical composition is HCO_3^- -Na-Mg, in Jura HCO_3^- - SO_4^{2-} -Na-Mg, in Ofatinti HCO_3^- - SO_4^{2-} -Mg-Na-Ca, in Crasnencoe HCO_3^- -Cl-Na. The waters are fresh, mineralisation rarely exceeds 1 g/l. In Dubasari district there are wells which pump only the Lower Sarmatian aquifer, with the upper part of the water-bearing strata below the sea level – in Cosnita, Lower Sarmatian is found on -6.8 m. The waters are fresh, mineralisation below 0.75 g/l. In Cosnita, the composition is HCO_3^- - SO_4^{2-} -Ca-Mg-Na, in Dubasari HCO_3^- -Na. In many areas of Dubasari district the wells use both Upper Badenian, Lower and Middle Sarmatian aquifers. In the district centre proper, the chemical data show a mixed, 3-anion and 3-cation composition of groundwaters, with HCO_3^- on the first place, and dominant Mg and Na among cations. In Tabuleuca, HCO_3^- is 76% and Na 62%, in Molovata Noua HCO_3^- stays at about 60-70%, Mg at 25-50% and Na more than 50%. In Cocieri SO_4^{2-} is dominant among anions at about 35-50%, and Mg at about 40-50%. In Crasnai Vinogradari and Alexandrovca Noua HCO_3^- is at 50-60% and Mg at about 60%. In Cosnita the waters of the Middle Sarmatian aquifer show the dominance of HCO_3^- at 65-70%, Mg at about 35-40%, Na at about 25-40%, and Ca at 25-35%. The mineralisation of the Middle Sarmatian groundwaters in Dubasari varies from 0.5 to 1.35 g/l. In both districts the concentration of Mg very often exceeds normal, about 6-7 mg-equiv/l. This, together with some concentration of Ca, makes the waters in the majority of areas and wells minerally hard, in many cases above 8-10 mg-equiv/l. Of other components, both Cl and SO_4^{2-} do not exceed normal quantities established by the standards of state. In both districts the groundwaters used in the communal sector are taken from the first, the upper aquifer in the pre-Quaternary rock strata.

Key words: *Sarmatian aquifers*, groundwater, chemical composition, mineralization, water horizon.

**CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE STUDY OF SAPROXYLIC
BEETLES (INSECTS: COLEOPTERA) FROM THE
REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA**

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The paper includes the first analysis of saproxylic beetles stored in 4 entomological collections in Chisinau city, as well as own materials collected between 2005 and 2022 from the reserves Codrii, Plaiul Fagului, Pădurea Domnească and Prutul de Jos, landscape reserve Codrii Tigheci, Hârbovăţ, Teliţa and some forest protection curtains in different country's districts.

As a result of investigation in the Republic of Moldova, were revealed 318 species of saproxylic beetles belonging to 212 genera and 44 families. Of these, 151 species are xylophagous, 57 polyphagous, 48 zoophagous, 40 mycophagous and 22 species are attributed to saprophagous, lichenophagous, parasitoid, phytophagous and coprophagous groups. Most of analyzed species are widespread: Palaearctic (80 species), Western Palaearctic (73), European (66), followed by Holarctic (21), Euro-Caucasian (19), Euro-Siberian (17) and cosmopolitan (14) species. The other 17 species are Mediterranean, Eurasian, Trans-Palaearctic and Near-Arctic.

The wide diversity of saproxylic insect species in forest ecosystems is an indicator of the state of the quality of the environment and also reflects the level of its functioning. For their development, saproxylic species require decaying wood. In the Republic of Moldova, forest management includes the evacuation of dead wood, most of which is removed from forest ecosystems, as a result, the number of saproxylic beetles in recent years has decreased dramatically.

According to the IUCN classification, only 14 species of saproxylic beetles are protected in the Republic of Moldova, of which 7 are critically endangered (CR), 2 endangered (EN) and 5 vulnerable (VU).

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Key words: *Saproxylic beetles*, entomological collections, forest ecosystems, indicator, quality of the environment.

STUDY IN THE FIELD OF REDUCING THE HARMFULNESS OF A BIODIESEL POWERED ENGINE

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Given that energy requirements are growing, that fossil fuel reserves are being depleted, and the polluting effects of their use on the ecosystem are catastrophic, it has become imperative to find new ways to produce energy from alternative sources to replace these classic fuels. One of the main directions for reducing toxic emissions is the use of alternative fuels for internal combustion engines. Particular emphasis is currently being placed on reducing the emissions of exhaust gases from diesel engines, due to the extension of their scope and the increase in the total number of vehicles equipped with diesel engines. Therefore, together with the improvement of the economic performance of diesel engines, reducing the toxicity of their exhaust gases becomes a major problem.

The studies are aimed at studying the influence of biofuel on the ecological performance of the engine, as well as identifying the practical possibility of using the optimal composition as fuel for MAC. For this, the values of the concentration of pollutant emissions from the exhaust gases generated by the combustion of biofuels were measured. The purpose of this research was to:

- establishing the values of experimental tests on pollutant emissions for various loads and speeds of diesel engine operation;
- analysis of exhaust emissions (carbon monoxide (CO), carbon dioxide (CO₂), hydrocarbons (C_nH_m) and particulate emissions (fumigation)) in the operation of the engine with fuels tested.

When carrying out the experimental tests in laboratory conditions (on stand), the gas analyser of the Cartec type CET 2000 series was used, in order to determine the concentration of the polluting emissions in the exhaust gases. As fuels, diesel was used, the mixtures B20 (diesel 80% + biodiesel 20%), B50 (diesel 50% + biodiesel 50%) and B100 (biodiesel 100%) transesterified from rapeseed oil at the biofuel production plant M8- KPB-01 developed by S.A. „Alimentarmaş”, t. Chisinau.

Research results have shown that:

- The use of biodiesel as fuel for the DC4 11,0/12,5 engine allowed reducing the CO emission concentration by 25% at the engine operating mode at an average load of 70-75%.
- With the increase of the biodiesel concentration in diesel, the emission of C_nH_m in the exhaust gases decreases, which shows us that in the cylinder the fuel practically burns completely. Hence, it is mentioned that the use of B100 biodiesel reduces the concentration of C_nH_m emissions in the exhaust gases compared to diesel by 37,5%.
- With the increase of the biodiesel concentration in diesel, it leads to a decrease of the smoke emission concentration in the exhaust gas of the engine DC4 11,0/12,5, which significantly improves the ecological parameters.

Experimental on-site research into the concentrations of pollutant emissions from the exhaust gases of the DC4 11,0/12,5 engine powered by B100 biodiesel and a mixture of biodiesel and diesel (B20, B50) reveals that the results obtained are dependent on complex, contradictory. The establishment of the best performances of the concentrations of harmful emissions in the exhaust gases is achieved by optimizing the composition of such biofuels.

Key words: alternative sources, harmful emissions, biofuels, engine powered, biodiesel, diesel.

EVALUAREA TENDINȚE ÎN MODIFICAREA STRUCTURII PEISAGISTICE PE EXEMPLUL BAZINULUI HIDROGRAFIC CUBOLTA

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Structura peisagistică caracteristică teritoriului Republicii Moldova a fost puternic influențată de presiunea tehnogenă asupra terenurilor. Documentele de politici de dezvoltare durabilă la nivel național au apărut pe ordinea de zi practic pe parcursul ultimilor două decenii, deși elementul de vulnerabilitate a teritoriului și capacitate de adaptare a acestuia a devenit indispensabil în ultimii ani ai perioadei indicate. Faptul indicat a fost determinat de dezvoltarea instrumentelor de analiză geospațială și apariția unor noi tehnici de evaluare și modelare în baza tehnologiilor informaționale geografice.

Figura 1. Model de utilizare a terenurilor din cadrul bazinului hidrografic Cubolta

Astfel, ca rezultat al interpretării imaginilor Landsat și aplicării clasificării în conformitate cu Sistemul FAO de Clasificare a acoperirii Terenului – Corine Land Cover Land Use a fost realizată harta privind modul de utilizare a terenurilor din cadrul bazinului hidrografic Cubolta. În rezultat se constată ponderea înaltă a terenurilor arabile (56464,5 ha) și frecvență mare a pășunilor (11266,7 ha). Metodologia de evaluare aplicată permite atribuirea bazinului hidrografic la terenuri cu ecologie instabilă (conform coeficientului de stabilitate ecologică), fiind evidentă capacitatea slăbită a teritoriului de absorbție a presiunii tehnogene.

Key words: structura peisagistică, bazinul hidrografic Cubolta, sistemul FAO, ecologie, presiunii tehnogene.

IRIS VARIEGATA (IRIDACEAE) IN THE FLORA OF LANDSCAPE RESERVE "CĂRBUNA"

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It is recognized that biological diversity is a natural wealth that underlies the functioning of ecosystems, the provision of ecosystem services essential to human well-being and contributes to the economic development of society.

Iris is the largest genus in the Iridaceae family with up to 300 species. Eight species have been indicated for the flora of the Republic of Moldova.

In recent years, during the planned research within the landscape reservation "Cărbuna" and the adjacent territories, the protected by law in the republic species *Iris variegata* L. – Variegated Iris has been reported. It is a plant with a thick brown rhizome. The stem is usually branched at the top or in the middle, wrapped at the base with the long sheaths of the leaves. Two or three leaves dry out during flowering, and the green ones have a length of 20-30 cm, at the top being narrow and acute. Flowers more frequent in number of 6 on the flowering stem. The leaflets of the back are slightly swollen, acute green or obtuse. External perigonal lacinae rounded at the tips, barbellate, golden-yellow, with narrow, yellow-rimmed edges with dark lilac or light-lilac venation.

According to our investigation in the reserve during 2020-22, the Variegated Iris grows alone or in small groups in clearings or in White oak forest edges, in plots 12, 13, 17, 18 and 19, in association with *Chrysaspis aurea* (Poll.) Greene, *Coronaria coriacea* (Moench) Schischk. et Gorschk., *Cotinus coggygia* Scop., *Crataegus monogyna* Jacq., *Cruciata laevipes* Opiz., *Dianthus armeria* L., *D. carthusianorum* L., *Erysimum cuspidatum* (Bieb.) DC., *Falcaria vulgaris* Bernh., *Ferulago galbanifera* (Mill.) Koch, *Gagea paczoskii* (Zapal.) Ghrossh., *G. villosa* (Bieb.) Duby, *Galatella linosyris* (L.) Reichenb. fil., *Galium mollugo* L., *G. octonarium* (Klok.) Soo, *Hypochaeris maculata* L., *Inula conyza* DC., *Leopoldia comosa* (L.) Parl., *Scorzonera cana* (C.A.Mey.) O.Hoffm., *Silene bupleuroides* L., *Ranunculus illyricus* L., *Salvia nemorosa* L., *S. verticillata* L., *Stachys recta* L., *Teucrium chamaedrys* L. etc.

In this context, the populations identified in the "Cărbuna" Landscape Reserve were monitored, the coordinates were taken and the limiting factors were identified. As conservation measures, we propose to protect the growing sites of this species, monitoring existing populations and recording parameters for the study of their dynamics. The inclusion of this taxon in the Red Book of the Republic of Moldova (4th edition) will contribute significantly to the protection and further distribution of the species both *ex-situ* and *in-situ*.

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Key words: *Iris variegata* L., "Cărbuna" Landscape Reserve, protect of species, monitoring, Red Book.

ADAPTATION OF THE METHOD FOR DETERMINING VITAMIN B₉ IN AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS

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Assessing the impact of natural waters pollution with chemical compounds is a complex and difficult process, especially at the stage of quantitative determination of pollutants in water composition, which are complex and multiphase systems. From a chemical point of view, pollution can be interpreted as the entrainment of the polluting compound in the processes of chemical self-purification and the shift of the dynamic equilibrium in the sense of the dominance of the reducing compounds. The pharmaceutical industry can become a dangerous source of natural waters pollution because pharmaceutical preparations contain biologically active substances. Once in the water, such substances not only upset the balance of self-purification processes, but can also show toxicity to hydrobionts.

Thus, in order to evaluate the intake of vitamin B₉, on the processes of chemical self-purification and the redox state of natural waters, the optimal conditions for modeling the systems in which vitamins have the role of potential pollutants were established. Vitamin B₉ is marketed as tablets, and 5 mg tablets were used in the study. Given that the modeled systems simulate the redox and photochemical processes of water self-purification, in which other substrates are present, such as hydrogen peroxide, transition metal ions (Cu, Fe), the selected spectrophotometric method must meet certain criteria, namely that other substrates must not interfere with the determination of the vitamin concentration. Secondly, it is necessary to select the optimal conditions for "preparation" of the vitamin solution from the pharmaceutical forms used, in order to obtain true results.

Vitamin B₉ in the form of tablets contains the following excipients: glucose and stearic acid. Therefore, the solution prepared in distilled water has turbidity. In order to eliminate the turbidity caused by stearic acid, 2 methods were applied: filtering through a simple paper filter and centrifugation ($V = 3500$ rpm, $t = 15$ min), and subsequently recorded the UV absorption spectra in the UV domain for comparison. Both procedures showed the same result, the absorption maximum wavelength for vitamin B₉ solution is 281 nm in both cases. The maximum absorption of vitamin B₉ solution allows its direct determination with the construction of the calibration curve $A = f(C)$, because this wavelength does not coincide with the absorption maximums of other substrates in the modeled systems. In order to demonstrate that the pH of the system does not influence the proposed spectrophotometric method, the UV absorption spectra were recorded at different pH values, respectively the wavelength of the absorption maximum is in all cases the same - 281 nm.

Further in the study of the legitimacy of the participation of vitamin B₉ in chemical self-purification processes of aquatic systems for the fast and effective quantitative determination, the spectrophotometric method will be used, based on the own absorption of the substrate in the UV spectrum.

Key words: vitamin B₉, chemical self-purification, redox state, natural waters, photochemical processes.

OPEN SCIENCE PRACTICE USED IN STRENGTHENING THE NATIONAL COLLECTION OF NON-PATHOGENIC MICROORGANISMS

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Microbiology is a field of biological science that studies microorganisms, most of interest and important are includes in collections for maintenance and distribution. But the requirements to the collections of microorganisms as a reliable and informationally associated biological material are increase.

National Collection of Non-Pathogenic Microorganisms (CNMN) functions at the Institute of Microbiology and Biotechnology and present an important depository of scientific and industrially valuable strains of microorganisms (fungi, yeasts, actinomycetes, bacteria, cyanobacteria, microalgae) in the Republic of Moldova. The digitalization, processing and standardization of CNMN scientific data facilitates their sharing and reuse between science and industry fields.

Research aim is to strengthen the National Collection of Non-Pathogenic Microorganisms by adopting open science practices on access, preservation, sharing and reuse of scientific data. The objectives:

- Conceptualization of CNMN according to the FAIR principles for scientific data (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital assets)
- Digitization, processing and standardization of Collection scientific date
- The development of CNMN digital tools (using Agile principles)
- Facilitating the integration of CNMN into the pan-European digital infrastructure MIRRI (Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure)

Open science is a policy priority for the European Commission (EC) and the standard method of working under its research and innovation funding programmes as it improves the quality, efficiency and responsiveness of research. It enables to store, curate and share research knowledge between partners from across academia, industry, public authorities, citizen groups and countries [1].

As a result of the project implementation, digital tools of National Collection of Non-Pathogenic Microorganisms information system will be developed, respecting the Open Science practices regarding the management of scientific data. This would enable preparing and submitting international projects related to microbial biodiversity and the application of microorganisms in various branches of the economy.

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References:

1. Open Science. European Commission website, 2021. Disponibil: https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en (accesat 28.06.2022)

Key words: non-pathogenic microorganisms, national collection, conceptualization of CNMN, digital tools, information system.

BACTERIAL VIABILITY AFTER 15 YEARS STORAGE

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Lyophilization, or freeze-drying, is a process is a widely applied effective method for the preservation of microorganisms. The National Collection of Nonpathogenic Microorganisms (NCNM) contains *Pseudomonas* sp., *Bacillus* sp. which are known for its antimicrobial activity, also lactic acid bacteria strains with important biotechnological properties for the dairy industry and prospective for starter cultures composition. It conservation and preservation for long-term storage present the purpose for the collection.

The aim of the research was to check the viability and stability of pure strains *Bacillus* sp. CNMN-BB-01, CNMN-BB-02, *Pseudomonas* sp. CNMN-PFB-01, CNMN-PsB-03 and lactic acid bacteria strains after 15 years storage in NCNM. Lactic acid bacteria pure cultures used in this study comprised *Lactococcus* sp. from CNMN-01 to CNMN-14 strains, *Streptococcus thermophilus* CNMN-15 and CNMN-16 strains.

The number of viable cells was determined as colony forming units per ml (CFU/ml). The survival rate was calculated as CFU/ml after freeze-drying divided by CFU/ml before freeze-drying.

Therefore, the results of this work show that *Bacillus* sp. and *Pseudomonas* sp. strains are viable and their titer was ranged from 6,8 to 7,6 $\log_{10}\text{UFCml}^{-1}$ for *Bacillus* and from 7,9 to 8,1 $\log_{10}\text{UFCml}^{-1}$ for *Pseudomonas*. It is known that *Pseudomonas* and *Bacillus* bacteria can be stored for over 30 years in freeze-dried form with no changes of high level cell viability at 6-7 $\log_{10}\text{UFCml}^{-1}$.

Similar research results on lactic acid bacteria strains after 15 years of storage in freeze-dried form demonstrated viability more than 80% with titer ranged from 6,2 to 8,3 $\log_{10}\text{UFCml}^{-1}$. According to other studies viability of species *Streptococcus*, *Staphylococcus*, *Brevibacterium*, *Pseudomonas*, *Corynebacterium*, *Lactobacillus*, *Salmonella*, *Bacillus* after freeze-drying amount to min. 70%. Thus, the numbers of viable cells remaining in the ampoules are sufficient to maintain the culture.

Microscopic smear appearance of strains investigated confirmed the purity of cultures, cell cultures represented rod-shaped cells typical of Gram-positive *Bacillus* sp. and Gram-negative *Pseudomonas* sp. Lactic acid bacteria cells present cocci and diplococci in the medium and long chains. Morphological and cultural properties correspond to the technological requirements for lactic acid bacteria species. All strains were able to active milk coagulation, formed firm, gel dense consistency, without eliminating of whey, without gas eruption.

Freeze-drying provides higher cell viability, is used for the long-term preservation, also it plays a fundamental role in scientific and practical fields. The obtained results confirm effectiveness of freeze-drying as a method of conservation through high ability to strains regeneration.

Acknowledgments: The research was funded out within the project 20.80009.7007.09 (ANCD).

Key words: bacterial viability, lyophilization, national collection, nonpathogenic microorganisms, long-term preservation.

THE RISK OF LATE SPRING FROSTS FOR AGRICULTURE OF THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA

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In the group of weather-climatic phenomena unfavorable to agriculture, frost occupies an important place. They cause not only the slowdown of plant development and the premature end of the vegetation cycle, but even their partial or total death. On the territory of the Republic of Moldova, according to the data of the State Hydrometeorological Service analyzed in this study for a period of over 60 years, late spring frosts are generated in anticyclones and their ridges formed in the Arctic air masses, as well as in high pressure areas with insignificant barricade gradients, oriented from west to east.

They can also occur as a result of the advection of cold air behind cyclones. Most often these frosts are advective-radiative. The mentioned frosts usually affect the layer in the immediate vicinity of the soil during the vegetation period of the plants, when the average daily air temperature remains positive.

In spring, frosts pose a great danger to agricultural crops, which are signaled after the stable passage of the average daily air temperature through 10°C in the direction of its increase (April 16-23). Spring frosts on average remain on the territory of Moldova until April 5-21, at the ground surface until April 22 - May 6. But the average dates of frost disappearance depend, to a large extent, on local conditions (fragmentation and height of landforms), sometimes reaching variations of 20-30 days. The latest date of frosts in the air in the north and center of the republic was reported on May 21-24 (1980), and in the south of the republic during the period 1-10 May (1990). Frosts are possible at the surface until June 1 (1955). In 1977 such a phenomenon took place between May 22-28.

Late spring frosts cause considerable damage to fruit crops during flowering. The probability of frost damage to apricot flowers and fruits is on average 15-40%, for other fruit crops - up to 15%. A special danger for the vine is the late spring frosts after the buds open. The most sensitive to frost are vegetable crops - such as tomatoes, peppers, eggplant and others are the most demanding to heat. Frosts with an intensity of 0-1°C cold lead to their extinction. The probability of frost damage to sprouted corn and sunflower plants is relatively low.

In practical interest, the risk interval for frost has been established, when the respective phenomena are the most dangerous, in order to avoid some of their serious consequences. The risk interval represents the interval between the average and extreme date of frost production. The risk range varies depending on the intensity of the genetic factors of the frost, as well as the local conditions, both as production time and as a place of manifestation. All methods used to reduce the consequences and control frost (fumigation, shelter, plant protection curtains, sprinkler and micro-sprinkler irrigation, air ventilation, hot air heating) must contribute to the reduction of radiative cooling, destruction of the thermal inversion layer from soil, homogenization of the air temperature in the microclimatic layer and consequently, maintenance of the air temperature and on the soil surface higher than 0°C.

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Key words: advective-radiative frosts, agriculture, damage to agricultural crops, risk interval for frost.

ON THE MECHANISM OF CHEMICAL SELF-PURIFICATION OF VARIOUS WATER SYSTEMS OF THE LOWER DNIESTER BASIN

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Identification of the participation of iron and copper in redox processes that occur in natural aquatic ecosystems allows us to make an assumption about the presence or absence of free radicals OH, intensively oxidizing organic substances of autochthonous and allochthonic origin, which is the essence of the mechanism of radical chemical self-purification. The presence of such a self-purification channel along with biological, can ensure the ecological prosperity of aquatic ecosystems and a high level of biodiversity of flora and fauna [1].

To identify the presence of a chemical self-purification channel in aquatic ecosystems of the Lower Dniester basin (small rivers, Dniester, reservoirs), a correlation and regression research method was used based on a database, including concentrations of various forms of metal migration and quality indicators of natural water.

The study carried out suggests that the oxidation of dissolved organic matter in the small rivers Ichel and Raut takes place by an ion-molecular mechanism, without the formation of free radicals. The migration of the studied metals is dominated by mineral forms, the dynamics of migration is of a pronounced seasonal nature.

In the segment of the Dniester from Dubasari to Vadul-lui-Voda, a change in the nature of the forms of migration of metals from mineral-organic to organic has been revealed. At the Vadul-lui-Voda cross-section, considerable involvement of copper in the processes of chemical self-purification was established. Iron, apparently, accumulates in bottom sediments and does not play a decisive role in the intensification of the radical processes of chemical self-purification in the studied segment of the Dniester.

The priority role of iron in the intensification of radical processes of chemical self-purification has been identified for the aquatic ecosystems of the reservoirs Ghidighici and Danceni. Copper, apparently, as a necessary trace element is accumulated by intensively developing biota of reservoirs.

As a result of the study, it is possible to conclude about irreversible problems with the ecological prosperity of the waters of Ichel and Raut, on the establishment of the Dniester cross-sections, where chemical self-purification processes are not intensive and about the greatest contribution of iron to the processes of chemical self-purification of reservoirs.

References:

1. Бородаев Р.И. Влияние различных форм миграции железа и меди на интенсивность редокс процессов водных систем Нижнего Днестра. In: *Hydropower Impact on River Ecosystem Functioning: Proceedings of the International Conference*, Tiraspol, Moldova, October 8-9, 2019, p.22-25.

Key words: aquatic ecosystems, chemical self-purification, Lower Dniester basin, redox processes, biodiversity of flora and fauna, metal migration, quality indicators.

SPATIAL MODELING OF DANGEROUS FROSTS IN THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA

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For the agriculture of the Republic of Moldova, the late spring and early autumn frosts present a great danger, because they can harm agricultural crops in the early stages of development or towards its end, thus creating frost damage, sometimes quite serious, depending on their resistance to frost.

Being located in the southeast of the continent, the territory of the republic is at the cross-road of several trajectories of the air masses movement that ultimately cause such phenomena as frost.

The possibilities of interconnecting the modules of GIS software, of analyzing the data obtained from field measurements and of organizing these data in structures such as meteorological models, lead to obtaining good results compared to the classical methodology.

For the spatial distribution of dangerous frosts, we used the Regional Geographic Information Systems. The date of manifestation of the first and last frost was interpolated, from 18 meteorological stations for the period 2005 - 2020.

The numerical model was obtained based on the regression equation (1, 2), without using the constant in the model, when performing the calculations, we used the number of calendar days (Julian date calendar).

The regression equation based on which the spring frosts' spatial distribution was modeled is: $Y=0,0505557*exp-0,0327863*habs-0,0305571*hrel+0,89103*panta-0,00000496262*x+0,00002212*y$ (1), where exp - slope's exposition, habs - absolute altitude, hrel - relative altitude, panta - the degree of inclination of the slopes, x, y - x and y coordinate respectively. Latitude X and longitude Y both are expressed in meters in WGS84 Transverse Mercator projection with 27° central meridian and false easting 500000 m.

The regression equation for the autumn frosts' spatial distribution is: $Y=0,0281752*exp+0,045071*habs+0,0166217*hrel-0,639479*panta+0,000070738*x+0,0000461509*y$ (2), where exp - slope's exposition, habs - absolute altitude, hrel - relative altitude, panta - the degree of inclination of the slopes, x, y - x and y coordinate respectively. Latitude X and longitude Y both are expressed in meters in WGS84 Transverse Mercator projection with 27° central meridian and false easting 500000 m.

As a result of the calculations performed, we conclude the following:

1. Dangerous frosts occur every year and have a spatial distribution throughout the study area.
2. A more in-depth study is required to be carried out for late spring frosts because both their duration and intensity threaten agricultural crops. For example, those registered in Soroca and Camenca on May 10, 2017.
3. The date of manifestation of early frosts as well as of late frosts has a negative impact on the vegetation, especially on agricultural crops, if they are manifested during the important phenological phases, causing economical damage to agriculture sector.

Key words: agricultural crops, damage, frosts spatial distribution, meteorological models.

CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE KNOWLEDGE OF LEAF BEETLES (CHRYSOMELIDAE) FROM ALFALFA

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The leaf beetles (Coleoptera, Chrysomelidae) family is one of the biggest of the order Coleoptera. The practical importance of the leaf beetles in the human activity draws the attention of the researchers permanently.

The faunistic materials were sampled in the alfalfa culture from Horești, Nișcani, Piatra Albă, Telița, Svetlii, Vulcănești, Vadul lui Isac, Călinești, Trifești and Saharna during May and June 2022. Most of the investigated fields were adjacent to a forest sector. The entomological net was used for collection. Some specimens were also gathered by hand from the leaves or soil surfaces.

A total number of 10 leaf beetles species belonging to 9 de genera and 5 subfamilies were identified all over the studied fields: *Cassida denticollis* Suffrian, 1844, *C. rubiginosa* Müller, 1776, *Chrysolina marginata* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Entomoscelis adonidis* (Pallas, 1771), *Galeruca tanaceti* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Gastrophysa polygona* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Gonioctena fornicata* (Brüggeman, 1873), *Oulema melanopus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Pachybrachis fimbriolatus* (Suffrian, 1848) and *Plagioderma versicolora* (Laicharting, 1781).

The species *Gonioctena fornicata*, a known pest of alfalfa was represented in all of studied fields. The lucerne leaf beetle usually feed more intensively at the stage of larva, that's why the larvae cause more damage than adult insects. Often the feeding on green parts of the plant leads to the worsening of the physiological condition of the plant attacked, and consequently to the decrease of harvest or to the plant growth decrease.

Considering that other herbaceous plant species can be found in the alfalfa fields, this explains the variety of leaf beetles collected: *Cassida denticollis*, *C. rubiginosa*, *Chrysolina marginata*, *Entomoscelis adonidis*, *Galeruca tanaceti*, *Gastrophysa polygona*, *Oulema melanopus* and *Pachybrachis fimbriolatus*. The presence of *Plagioderma versicolora* is accidental because it feeds exclusively on leaves and pollen of willow and poplar trees and can be explained by the existence of forest next to the field.

The investigations will continue throughout the growing season of alfalfa and the list can be supplemented with other leaf beetles species.

Acknowledgments: The study was performed under the project 20.80009.7007.02. „Evolutionary changes of economically important terrestrial fauna, of rare and protected species under anthropogenic and climatic changes”.

Key words: *Chrysomelidae*, alfalfa, decrease of harvest, leaf beetles species, variety.

**INERSPECIFIC BEHAVIOUR BETWEEN *APODEMUS FLAVICOLLIS* AND
APODEMUS SYLVATICUS FEMALES
FROM URBAN ECOSYSTEMS OF CHIȘINĂU CITY,
REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA**

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Recently many studies have described the effects of urbanization on species behavior and adaptation. The species *Apodemus uralensis* and *A. sylvaticus* were captured with live traps in urban ecosystems of Chișinău city. The study of the interspecific relations between the two species were carried out by the method of pair encounters.

In interspecific relations of *A. uralensis* and *A. sylvaticus* various types of olfactory contacts were established: naso-nasal, naso-lateral, naso-dorsal, naso-ventral. In the interspecific contacts of the females, aggressive elements were registered, but in small numbers. *A. sylvaticus* females explored the environment (36.9% of the experiment duration) and actively tried to familiarize themselves with the partner – the number of contact initiations increased 2 times compared to intraspecific contacts and was 2.4 times higher than the analogous index of females *A. uralensis*. In *A. uralensis* females the complex of defensive behavior increased considerably: practically at each contact initiation, they responded through aggressive postures or shrill sounds. The duration of the freezing was 2 times longer than that of the exploratory activity, while the last one decreased by 1.3 times. Compared to intraspecific contacts, the noise level increased 3.7 times and the number of aggressive postures - 5.2 times.

According to the obtained data, the reciprocal olfactory contacts (naso-nasal, naso-anal, naso-lateral) have a great importance for the social relations of rodents and depend on the social status, season and sex of the partners. When the specimens of different species are placed in pairs, the olfactory contacts last 10 - 40 sec. The number of olfactory contacts is maximum in the first 5 minutes of the experiment, during the establishment, the formation of mutual relations between animals.

All the listed characteristics of representatives of *A. sylvaticus* allow us to conclude that this species has high adaptive abilities, great potential and resistance to overcome the negative conditions of "tension" community.

Acknowledgments: The study was carried out within State Program project 20.80009.7007.02.

Key words: *Apodemus sylvaticus*, *Apodemus uralensis*, \adaptation, behavior, intraspecific contacts, urban ecosystems.

CLIMATIC AND HYDROMETEOROLOGICAL PHENOMENA OF RISK ON THE TERRITORY OF THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA

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The paleoclimate of the planet Earth demonstrates the cyclicity and evolution of the climate for certain geological periods of the Earth manifested in time and space, where flora and fauna have confronted and adapted to certain climatic conditions and hydrometeorological phenomena.

Weather and climate have been and are the basic elements of the planet Earth that condition and influence the daily existence and evolution of both man and the environment.

The weather and climate parameters monitored for a period of more than 30 years have become climatic norms, and serve as benchmarks both for anthropogenic activities and for the state and evolution of the environment.

But deviations from the climate norm are classified as climatic and hydrometeorological risk phenomena, so the greater the gap from the climate norm, the greater the intensity and damage caused by hydrometeorological risk phenomena, sometimes reaching catastrophic levels.

The territory of the Republic of Moldova in the context of climate change is increasingly affected by risky climatic and hydrometeorological phenomena, such as: storms, heat waves, cold waves, gusts of wind, storms, torrential rains, floods, hail, droughts, late frosts. In this article I made the statistical analysis of the evolution and of the damages produced as a result of the production of the climatic and hydrometeorological phenomena of risk from the period 2007-2021.

Fig.1 Number of climatic and hydro meteorological phenomena of risk (2007-2021)

The material damages caused by the climatic and hydrometeorological phenomena of risk have a direct impact on the socio-economic development of the country. World experience has shown that the most vulnerable countries to climate and hydrometeorological risk are poorly developed or developing countries such as the Republic of Moldova, because they do not have the financial support for national programs to adapt to climate change.

Fig. 2. Material damages caused by climatic and hydrometeorological phenomena of risk (2007-2021)

At the same time, the statistical analysis of the data provided by the General Inspectorate for Emergency Situations showed which of the climatic and hydrometeorological phenomena most often have deviations from the climatic norm and consequently cause major material losses and also what is their tendency.

Key words: climate change, climate norm, climate parameters, risk phenomena, material damages.

PARASITE FAUNA IN PYGMY FIELD MOUSE FROM VARIOUS BIOTOPES OF THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA

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The pygmy field mouse (*Apodemus uralensis*, Pallas, 1771) inhabits the forest edge, forest shelter belts and the open type biotopes: meadows, pastures, agrocenoses, fallow ground. It is well adapted to more arid conditions in comparison to other *Apodemus* species, therefore it is widely spread over the republic territory. It is a species with a lower frequency compared to other small rodents and has accessory ecological significance. The rodents are the basic trophic component of carnivorous mammals and prey birds, being the hosts (intermediate, definitive) that contain various invasive forms of a large range of parasitic species specific to other animals and humans.

The aim of the paper was the ecoparasitological study of *A. uralensis*, in order to establish the structural diversity of parasite fauna from various biotopes of the Republic of Moldova.

The results of parasitological investigations showed a prevalence of *Catenotaenia cricetorum* of 5.0%, respectively of *Hydatigera taeniaeformis larvae* – 10.0%, *Taenia pisiformis larvae* – 10.0%, *Rodentolepis straminea* – 5.0%, *Paranoplocephala omphaloides* of 10.0%, *Skrjabinotaenia lobata* – 10.0%, *Syphacia obvelata* – 20.0%, *Syphacia stroma* – 5.0%, *Capillaria hepatica* – 15.0%, *Heligmosomoides polygyrus* – 5.0%, *Mastophorus muris* – 20.0%, *Trichocephalus muris* – 15.0% and invasion with *Strongyloides ratti* – 15.0%.

The taxonomic structure consists of 3 classes, 10 families, 12 genera and 13 species, of which 6 parasitic species belong to the Cestoda class (*T. pisiformis larvae*, *S. lobata*, *H. taeniaeformis*, *C. cricetorum*, *R. straminea*, *P. omphaloides*), with a share of 46.1% of the species, 5 species - to the Secernentea class (*S. obvelata*, *S. stroma*, *H. polygyrus*, *M. muris*, *S. ratti*) with a share of 38.5%, and 2 species - to the Adenophorea class (*T. muris*, *C. hepatica*), constituting 15.4% of the total identified species.

The data obtained prove the potential of the parasitic pollution risk of the interfering area between natural and anthropized ecosystems and as a result the transmission of invasive forms from wild animals to domestic animals and to humans. At the same time, the rodents as component of the trophic chain are vectors of invasive forms in the environment and ensure the functional stability of the host-parasitic systems within the investigated biocoenoses.

Acknowledgments: The studies were performed within the State Program projects 20.80009.7007.12 „Diversity of hematophagous arthropods, zoo- and phytohelminths, vulnerability, strategies for tolerating climatic factors and elaboration of innovative procedures for integrated control of socio-economic interest species” and 20.80009.7007.02 „Evolutive changes of economically important terrestrial fauna, of rare and protected species in the conditions of anthropic and climatic changes”.

Key words: *Apodemus uralensis*, host-parasitic systems, parasite fauna, parasitic pollution risk.

**CONTRIBUTION TO THE STUDY OF *FAGOPYRUM ESCULENTUM*
MOENCH IN THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA**

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The flora of the Republic of Moldova is rich in species of honey plants, with high productivity of honey, plants that provide food for insects throughout the year, except for the cold season. In the collection of Honey and Forage Plants of the "Alexandru Ciubotaru" National Botanical Garden (Institute) (NBGI), there is a wide range of valuable plants, with multiple potential uses, in particular – as honey crops. Among them, there are species that start vegetating in early spring and start blooming in early May. The study of flowering dynamics allows highlighting the generative stages of plants and the most active periods when honey insects collect nectar and pollen. *Fagopyrum esculentum* Moench (family Polygonaceae Juss.), common buckwheat, is a valuable herbaceous, annual plant, with edible seeds, included in the group of pseudocereals. It is also cultivated as a honey plant. Depending on the weather conditions, in 12-14 days after sowing, the cotyledons of the seedlings emerge on the soil surface. At this moment, the vegetative phase begins, consisting of the seedling, immature and virginal stages, characterized by the active growth of the vegetative organs of plants (stems, lateral branches and leaves), which lasts about 20-25 days from the emergence of seedlings. Buckwheat plants can reach up to 125 cm in height, the stem is erect and branched. Usually, there are 6-12 leaves on each branch. The generative phase begins with the development of floral buds. Flowering is long, staggered and lasts about 33-48 days. In the full flowering stage, on a medium-sized shoot (85 cm), with 3-4 branches, there are 22-24 inflorescences at different stages of development. On one inflorescence, at the same time, there can be flower buds, flowers and developing fruits. The number of flowers on a shoot varies between 375 and 400, and the fruits – about 92-125. A buckwheat plant can produce around 1-1.5 thousand flowers [1]. The flowers are attractive to pollinating insects, as a source of nectar and pollen, especially under conditions of high temperatures and humidity. A flower lives for about 24 hours and produces up to 0.1 mg of sugar [2]. Pollinating insects are more active on buckwheat flowers until 11.00 on days with high temperatures. Common buckwheat, *Fagopyrum esculentum* Moench, can be sown as a primary crop or as a successive crop, the potential honey productivity reaches values of 70-90 kg honey/ha [1]; the dehulled seeds contain 12.6% protein, large amounts of threonine and lysine, vitamin E, folic acid. The identification, mobilization and acclimatization of new high-potential honey plants, will contribute to the expansion of the range of honey crops and ensure a continuous source of pollen and nectar, very important for the health and well-being of honeybee families.

Acknowledgments: The study has been carried out in the framework of the project: 20.80009.5107.02 “Mobilization of plant genetic resources, plant breeding and use as forage, melliferous and energy crops in bioeconomy”.

References: 1. Бурмистров А., Никитина В. Медоносные растения и их пыльца. Москва: Росагропромиздат. 1990. 192 с.; 2. Нестеров П., Пинчук Л., Леонтьяк Г. Медоносные ресурсы Молдавии. Кишинев. Карта Молдовеняскэ. 1988.205 с.

Key words: *Fagopyrum esculentum*, flowering dynamics, honey crops, honey productivity, source of nectar and pollen.

CYANOBACTERIUM *NOSTOC LINCKIA* GROWTH UNDER DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF COPPER(II) IONS

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Cyanobacteria are ecologically significant prokaryotes that can be found in heavy metals contaminated environments. In these situations, they can act as bioremediators of pollutants, especially heavy metal ions, by sequestering the metal ions on the surface of their cells due to the presence of negatively charged hydroxyl (OH), carboxyl (COOH), carbonyl (C=O), sulfhydryl (SH), and other functional groups that are available to bind with positively charged metal ions. In cyanobacteria, copper plays an essential role as a structural component of plastocyanin, which mediates the electron transport chain, and also an essential cofactor of enzyme superoxide dismutase. However, at higher concentrations (more than 3.0 mg/L), copper is reported to be toxic to microorganisms. Consequently, higher metal contents are transferred to higher trophic levels of the food chain. The permissible limit of Cu^{2+} in water is between 0.05 and 1.5 ppm, and has many health risks associated with the exposure to excess Cu^{2+} in humans. Abnormally high copper levels have been associated with a number of diseases, including neurodegenerative disorders such as Alzheimer's, Parkinson's, and prion diseases.

In this work, the effect of divalent copper ion (Cu^{2+}) exposure was studied on cyanobacterium *Nostoc linckia* growth. A sulfate salt of copper, namely copper(II) sulfate pentahydrate, was used as a source of metallic ions. The copper concentrations chosen for the study were 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 5.0, 10 and 20 mg/L, which were added to the culture in the exponential growth phase of the life cycle. *Nostoc* growth was determined spectrophotometrically at the end of cultivation cycle, which lasted 12 days.

The data showed no significant decrease in the amount of biomass in the case of *Nostoc* growth under the lowest concentrations of copper ions. Hence, in metallic monosystems with 0.1, 0.5 and 1.0 mg/L copper ions, cyanobacterial biomass produced during cultivation cycle was about 1.0 g/L, which means a reduction of up to 15% compared to control. In the case of further metal concentrations such as 1.5, 2.0 and 2.5 mg/L, *Nostoc* growth has sharply decreased up to 32% in comparison with control. Then, the cultivation of cyanobacterial strain under conditions of higher concentrations of copper 5.0, 10.0 and 20.0 mg/L did not have a significant effect on the reduction of biomass production. At the same time, the data were comparable with the cultivation of the culture under conditions of low concentrations of copper ions. Thus, we can see a wave type effect of *Nostoc linckia* growth under various concentrations of metallic copper.

The release of polysaccharides by some cyanobacterial strains has been one of the mechanisms to overcome metal toxicity. The increase in the amount of exopolysaccharides synthesized by *Nostoc* in response to higher concentrations of copper and the protective role of these molecules may explain the wave type effect of *Nostoc linckia* exposure to different concentrations of copper.

Key words: *Nostoc linckia*, bioremediators, concentrations of copper ions, cultivation cycle, food chain, health risks, heavy metal ions,

THE ROLE OF CLIMATE FACTORS IN THE PROCESS OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION IN MOLDOVA

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The agricultural sector of the Republic of Moldova is most influenced by climate variability, given the dependence of agriculture on the evolution of weather on those periods of crop vegetation, as well as increasing the frequency, duration and intensity of weather and climate risks in the context of regional climate change. The effects of regional climate change are significant and expressed by changing the main environmental variables (air temperature and precipitation), the impact on agricultural plant development being increasingly evident.

The daily temperature regime is the one that imprints the biological evolution of the cultivated plants and offers a closer image of the reality of the temperature variations that can occur, sometimes reaching extreme values, which constitute climatic risks through negative effects. Thus, the persistence and continuity of positive daily average temperatures between April and September for the territory of the Republic of Moldova, indicate favorable thermal conditions for various annual or perennial crops. At the same time, tropical temperatures, above 30-35°C, impose restrictions on plant development, reducing agricultural production.

Atmospheric precipitation registers relatively low multiannual averages (470-620 mm), this being the main characteristic of the climate in the region. The results of our investigations note that the drought limiting factor that manifests itself on the largest agricultural area of the country, and in this context, data indicate that the most vulnerable agricultural areas are located in the south and center of the republic, except for partial land, located in the meadows of large rivers.

According to the analyzed data, in the last two decades there have been several years with strong and very strong droughts (2003, 2007, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2020), which have led to the decrease of fruit in most agricultural crops, causing significant direct losses, estimated at about \$ 1.0-1.25 billion each. Also, analysis of the results obtained on road losses to the main agricultural crops, it was found that in all the dry years of the analyzed decades, sunflower recorded the lowest losses compared to other field crops, due to ecological plasticity and potential, greater adaptation of sunflower to regional climate change.

It is very important that the knowledge and identification of meteorological risks with negative effects on crop stability be based on both early warning systems on dangerous meteorological phenomena and on technological practices applied in relation to the current evolution of climatic conditions and foreseeable future scenarios. Thus, possibilities to adapt to the effects of climate change aim to reduce the impact on the agricultural production process and are mainly based on optimizing the duration of the vegetation period of crops, resistance of genotypes to extreme temperatures (heat, cold / frost), deficits / excesses water in the soil and increase their risk of phytopathogens, ecological plasticity, tolerance to the effects of extreme weather events.

Key words: agriculture, climate variability, climate risks, droughts, vulnerable areas.

MICROBIOLOGICAL TOOLS FOR ASSESSING IMPACTS ON SOIL ORGANIC MATTER CONTENT

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Soil organic matter (SOM) is fundamental to soil quality and has been suggested as the single most important indicator of soil quality and productivity. For any given soil and climate, the amount of SOM is determined by land use and soil management, but the usefulness of SOM data for soil quality monitoring is constrained by the difficulty of experimentally verifying changes over short periods of time. Long-term experiments seem to offer only a partial solution to this problem.

Soil microorganisms accounts for only 1-3 per cent of total soil organic carbon, but they play a key role in the soil forming processes, including in SOM transformations.

Significant correlations between SOM content and soil microbial parameters (soil microbial biomass, and/or basal respiration, and/or metabolic quotient) were observed in the moderately and poorly humified Typical chernozems from the Moldovan long-term field experiments that included 6 traditional (10-field) and 5 ecological (7-field) crop rotations (with and without alfalfa, mineral fertilizers and/or farmyard manure), continuous black fallow, and 5 continuous crops (with and without mineral fertilizers with farmyard manure). These correlations open practical possibilities of using soil microbial parameters as a tool for timely SOM related assessments and predictions. Once a new soil management practice is introduced, the substantial difference in the soil microbial biomass (SMB) and SOM turnover rates will allow the soil microbial parameters to reach a new equilibrium (reflecting the peculiarities of this management) much sooner than the SOM content. As soon as that equilibrium of the microbial parameters is established, the future SOM content becomes predictable/calculable from the established correlational relationships, assuming that given enough time SOM will tend to fit the same correlational relationship that was observed in the long-term field experiments. These predictions may be beneficial in such important fields as protection and enhancement of soil quality and biodiversity, carbon sequestration, development/assessment of sustainable soil management practices, and others. The implementation of the possibility may provide farmers with better opportunities for investing into soil quality/biodiversity and may contribute to solving problems related to the climate change and others.

Acknowledgments: The presented results were obtained within two research projects: (a) Project "Microbiological tools for assessment and prediction of the impact of soil management on soil organic carbon in high-organic black soils of Moldova" financially supported by the FAO in the framework of the global project GCP /GLO/853/RUS, and (b) Project 20.80009.7007.03 "Microbial tools for degradation of non-recyclable plastics waste" financially supported by National Agency for Research and Development, the Republic of Moldova.

Key words: correlational relationships, soil organic matter, soil quality, sustainable soil management.

STORAGE POTENTIAL OF TRITICALE ACCESSIONS - INDICATOR OF THEIR VIABILITY UNDER *EX SITU* CONSERVATION

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The purpose of this research was to study the morphophysiological and biochemical parameters of triticle seeds after accelerated aging (AA) test. The storage potential (SP) of collection accessions in active collections of the gene bank was characterized with the purpose of their *ex situ* conservation, and to reveal genotypic differences of genotypes. According to the plan, triticle seeds genotypes should be grouped by their potential capability to preserve viability of samples exposed to high temperature and humidity.

Objects of studies were collection accessions of triticle seeds from active collection of the plant gene bank. SP of seeds was determined by two tests: test for accelerated aging of seeds by Safina & Filipenko method (2013) and test for electrical conductivity of solutions (EC), both are included in the International Rules for Seed Testing (ISTA). AA-test of seeds was conducted under the increased air temperature (37°C), humidity of seeds 13%, high relative humidity (98%), aging time was 30 days. During this test various morphophysiological parameters of seeds and seedlings were measured every week (dynamic measurement) according to the ISTA: germinating power (GP) and germinability (G) of seeds, radicle length (RL), fresh and dry biomass of radicles. EC of solutions with normal and aged seeds was measured by conductometer N5721M. With regard to biochemical parameters, the activity of the peroxidase enzyme (PO) was measured in radicles of seedlings. The experiment was conducted in quadruplicate. Aged seeds were sprouted in Petri dishes in thermostat at 25°C. Experimental data were processed using the software *Statistica 7*. According to the set of different parameters of triticle seeds after the AA-test of seeds, the following genotypes had the highest SP: *Ingen 3*, *Ingen 33*, *Ingen 35*, *Ingen 40*, *Ingen 54*, *Ingen 93* (loss of seed germination after AA-test by 35%) and the lowest storage potential was found in *Ingen 2 and Ingen 4* (loss of seed germination by 70%). The smallest drop of other parameters was in genotypes with high SP (raw root biomass-by 100 mg, root length-by 2 mm). Conclusions: 1. Use of AA-test of seeds and determination of their different parameters allowed assessment of SP of triticle collection accessions from the active collection of the gene bank. 2. It was demonstrated that EC of solutions with aged seeds of the most genotypes of triticle is higher than that of solutions with normal seeds. 3. Significant positive correlation of germinability of triticle seeds with germinating power, radicle length, fresh and dry biomass of seedlings was revealed after conduction of test for AA of seeds.

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Key words: accelerated aging test, *ex situ* conservation, morphophysiological parameters of seeds, triticle.

THE IMPACT OF PRECIPITATION ON THE SUNFLOWER CROP IN THE NORTHERN REGION OF THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA

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In the conditions of the continental climate with excessive nuances, characterized by a great variability in time of the climatic elements, specific to the territory of the Republic of Moldova, the amount of precipitation is one of the most important factors that determine the optimal growth and development of agricultural crops, including sunflower, determining the greatest differentiations in time and space of the average harvest value per hectare. Thus, in the conditions of the Republic of Moldova, the amount of precipitation, most of the times is rather a limiting factor.

Knowing the amount of atmospheric precipitation during the growing season, forecasting assessments of the productivity value can be carried out. The results obtained by Cojocari R., reveal that they vary on the territory of the country between the limits of 340-450 mm. Starting from these values, we find that a more favorable situation is outlined during the vegetation period of the sunflower, when, especially in the northern part of the region, there are also some quantitative surpluses of precipitation compared to the optimal required. Thus, the isohieta with the value of 375 mm – the optimal quantity for the period April- October – crosses the districts of Riscani, Edinet, Donduseni and Ocnita. Within the region, based on the data from the period 2007-2020, it appears that the most favorable districts for the cultivation of sunflower are Glodeni, Ocnita and Edinet. The districts with the lowest performances in the development of the sunflower culture are Singerei, Floresti and Soroca.

In sunflowers, although rainfall amounts in the cold half of the year correspond as a spatial distribution with the average fruit distribution, in terms of quantity, they are insufficient for the entire region. Instead, the precipitation amounts from the growing season allow to highlight the north of the country where the average values of the period 2007-2020 are within the optimal needs.

The use of modern agrotechnical processes that help to effectively use the moisture accumulated in the soil. The mechanized work of the soil reduces the use of moisture by evaporation, improves the aeration of the soil. But the use of the appropriate agricultural technique and the application of the correct methods of rotation are possible only on large agricultural areas. So, it would require a consolidation of agricultural land.

Acknowledgments: This study was funded by the project of the State Program 20.80009.5107.01 - Genetico-molecular and biotechnological studies of the sunflower in the context of sustainable management of agricultural ecosystems.

Key words: agricultural technique, amount of precipitation, isohieta, limiting factor, sunflower, spatial distribution.

ECOTOURISM POTENTIAL OF BIODIVERSITY FROM CRIULENI DISTRICT, REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA

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The biodiversity of the living world, through the richness of floristic and faunal species, has always been the points of tourist attraction. A special interest for tourists who practice ecological tourism, presents the protected natural areas of this district. Thus, according to the field studies and in accordance with the Law on the fund of natural areas protected by the state no. 1538-XIII of 25.02.98, in the Criuleni district, the following protected natural areas of interest for the practice of ecological tourism are: **I. Monuments of nature (A. Geological and paleontological: Fossil soils on the Transnistrian terraces; Goian outcrop; Surprises cave** (The fauna of the cave is made up of several species of bats (mainly of the *Myotis* and *Rhinolophus* genera), but also terrestrial invertebrates such as pseudoscorpions, arachnids, myriapods, terrestrial crustaceans et al. There are also several species of flora in the cave. Saprophytic fungi grow here (including a species of phosphorescent mushrooms); **B. Hydrological: The mineral springs from Onițcani village** (The protection zone is sprinkled with clumps of trees, the adjacent land being covered by forest plantations); **C. Botanical - Representative sectors with forest vegetation: Poplar forest** (from trees comprises 94 specimens of *Populus alba*, 2 of *Ulmus laevis* and 1 of *Pyrus pyraeaster*, from shrubs are present *Prunus spinosa*, *Swida sanguinea*, *Crataegus monogyna* and *Rosa canina*); **Pogorele** (15 species of trees were identified – *Acer campestre*, *Acer negundo*, *Acer platanoides*, *Acer tataricum*, *Carpinus betulus*, *Cerasus avium*, *Fraxinus excelsior*, *Morus alba*, *Populus alba*, *Pyrus pyraeaster*, *Quercus robur*, *Salix alba*, *Tilia cordata* et al.; 12 species of shrubs including *Corylus avellana*, *Crataegus monogyna*, *Euonymus europaea* et al.); **Secular trees - 3 in number**. According to Annex no. 3 of the Law on the fund of natural areas protected by the state, in Criuleni district there are 3 secular trees - 2 pedunculate oaks and a poplar from Canada. **II. Forest nature reserves: Dubăsari, Zoloceni, III. Monuments of landscape architecture: The park from Bălăbănești village** (from trees, the species are still preserved are: *Sophora japonica*, *Quercus imbricaria*, *Koelreuteria paniculata*, *Maclura aurantiaca*, *Pinus silvestris*, *Pinus strobus* et al., and from planted shrubs – *Rosa canina* and *Syringa vulgaris*), **The park from Miclesti village** (among the species of trees and shrubs attested in the park are: *Acer platanoides*, *Acer pseudoplatanus*, *Acer campestre*, *Aesculus hippocastanum*, *Juglans regia*, *Fraxinus excelsior*, *Populus alba*, *Populus pyramidalis*, *Ulmus pumila*, *Ulmus laevis*, *Cerasus avium*, *Tilia tomentosa*, *Buxus sempervirus*, *Pyrus communis*, *Robinia pseudoacacia*, *Abies nordmanniana*, *Pinus nigra*, *Picea abies*, *Biota orientalis*).

Thus Criuleni district has a rich ecotourism potential consisting of objectives and natural complexes taken under state protection: 3 monuments of geological and paleontological nature, 1 monument of hydrological nature, 2 monuments of botanical nature represented by representative sectors with forest vegetation, 2 forest nature reserves, 2 monuments of landscape architecture – rich in a significant variety of floristic and faunal species, as well as 3 secular trees.

Key words: biodiversity, ecological tourism, forest vegetation, landscape architecture, protected natural areas, variety of species.

ASPECTS REGARDING THE ECOLOGICAL SITUATION OF SOME PROTECTED AREAS IN CHISINAU MUNICIPALITY

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Currently, it is necessary to address the problems of biodiversity conservation at the geosystemic, ecosystemic and species levels. Particular attention must be paid to protected natural areas intended for the protection and conservation of plant communities and valuable wildlife habitats, and this is clearly felt in urban areas as well.

In Chisinau municipality, according to the Law on the fund of state protected natural areas no. 1538-XIII of 25.02.1998, there are 4 natural objects protected by the state: Zoo - 24.27 ha; Dendrological Garden - 83 ha; National Museum of Ethnography and Natural History - 0.075 ha; “Valea Morilor” culture and leisure park - 113.9 ha, as well as secular trees - 63 units.

The Zoo is a Scientific Institution for culturalization and training. During 2021, the correctness of the requirements for the rational use of the faunal collections as well as of the species from the animal kingdom in captivity was kept under control and verified.

Dendrological Garden has rich vegetation. During 2021, the administration of the institution did not request the Environmental Protection Agency to coordinate the forestry works. At the same time, it should be mentioned that the ecological condition of the park is satisfactory.

The National Museum of Ethnography and Natural History is a Monument of landscape architecture and guarantees the conservation and protection of the faunal and floristic collections within the botanical garden and the vivarium of the institution. The secular trees managed by the respective Museum are in a satisfactory condition, their protection regime is respected, information plates are installed.

The “Valea Morilor” culture and leisure park has the status of an architectural and landscape monument, the owner being the Chisinau City Hall. During 2021, forestry works were coordinated in relation to the vegetation proposed by the Municipal Enterprise of the Green Spaces Management Association. The vegetable kingdom is relatively rich. There are 63 secular trees in the field. The Agency for Environmental Protection for the period 2021, drafted letters to the beneficiaries of the lands in whose management are secular trees, through which it was made known the need to ensure the protection regime. Protected natural areas operate in accordance with the Framework Regulations, developed for each of their categories. The regime for the administration of the protected areas fund represents a unitary set of protection, ecological and technical-organizational measures that regulate the activity carried out within the natural objectives. The specific elements of the protected areas in Chisinau municipality correspond to the category of protection and their condition is satisfactory.

Key words: biodiversity conservation, protected natural areas, secular trees, urban areas.

ASSESSMENT OF THE ANTHROPOGENIC IMPACT ON THE WATER QUALITY OF THE LOWER DNIESTER TRIBUTIES

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It has been established that in all sections of the rivers under study, cases of pollution by biogenic substances have been identified, which differ both in the concentrations of their excesses and in the cases of their detection. The excess in the nitrogenous group dominates in the tributaries: Bull, Ikel, Botna. In the Reut tributary, the groups of nitrogen and phosphate pollutants are equal.

The most unfavorable sections of the river were identified, which were Botna, Ikel, where excesses were recorded for all nutrients and had a degree of pollution higher than in the tributaries of the Reut and Byk. It is shown that the assessment of water quality in rivers from an ecological point of view, inflows according to the same indicators had different quality classes. However, class V was defined in all river ecosystems, which indicates the fact of an increased anthropogenic load, associated primarily with the entry of pollutants into the rivers, both recent and permanent pollution.

Key words: biogenic substances, lower Dniester tributies, nitrogen pollutants, phosphate pollutants, water quality.

MICROBIOLOGICAL POLLUTION OF SMALL TRIBUTIES OF THE LOWER PART OF THE DNIESTR

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It has been established that bacteriological pollution with concentrations of thermotolerant coliform bacteria and total coliform bacteria was recorded in all tributaries, however, the level of pollution varies significantly, which indicates a significant degree of anthropogenic load along the rivers and different volumes of pollutants.

It has been proved that the highest degree of pollution on the right side of the Dniester is for the Byk tributary, and on the left side of the river, it was found for the Svetlyi stream, but its degree of bacteriological pollution is lower than in the Byk tributary. According to the estimated bacteriological indicators, the degree of pollution of the tributaries was characterized and classified from “moderate” to “extremely high” pollution level, which indicates a possible discharge of domestic wastewater into tributaries from households located along the coast that do not have a centralized network of domestic sewerage.

Key words: anthropogenic load, bacteriological indicators, bacteriological pollution, lower Dniester tributies, thermotolerant bacteria.

CYTOTOXIC EFFECT OF NANOCOMPOSITES BASED ON VANADIUM OXIDES

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Nanomaterials are widely used in various fields: medical, commercial and industrial production practices [1]. Despite the rapid progress and early acceptance of nanotechnologies, their potential for various adverse effects on humans, non-human biota and ecosystems is still not well elucidated. In this context, in recent years, there has been a rapid increase in experimental studies on the toxicity and biological hazards of nanomaterials in the environment [2].

In this paper we aimed to study the cytotoxic effects of nanocomposites based on vanadium oxides on onion meristematic cells.

In the experiment were used the pyroceramic plates coated with thin layers of VO₂, V₂O₃ and V₂O₅, of nanometric dimensions [3]. Onion was selected as the model specimen for cytotoxicity assessment, which was exposed to nanocomposites for different time (48h and 72h), prior to germination. For cytological studies, root with a length of 1-2 cm were taken. Washing, fixation, hydrolysis, staining and preparation were performed according to the standard methodology of staining and observation of chromosomes [4].

According to the results of the cytological study, the exposure of the seeds to the action of nanocomposites based on vanadium oxides, induces changes in the values of mitotic index, comparative control. At the same time, fluctuations in the values of the phase indices of mitosis were recorded. Disruption of cell division phases indicates that vanadium oxide-based nanocomposites alter mitotic activity by cytoskeleton disorder and interfere with mitotic spindle formation, as confirmed by the occurrence of abnormal mitoses: C-mitoses, disturbed metaphase, ana-telofase spindle disorders, sticky chromosomes with bridge, vagrant chromosomes and fragments. Cells with 1-2 micronuclei and binucleated cells have also been identified, which are an indicator of the above-mentioned mutations [5].

Our results demonstrated that exposure of onion to nanocomposites based on vanadium oxides causes cytotoxicity and genotoxicity.

References:

1. Chen X., Schluessener H. Nanosilver: a nanoparticle in medical application. *Toxicol. Lett.*, 2008. Nr.176, p.1-12.
2. Cheng-Teng Ng., Jasmine J. Li, Boon-Huat Bay and Lin-Yue Lanry Yung Current Studies into the Genotoxic Effects of Nanomaterials. *Journal of Nucleic Acids*, 2010. Article ID 947859, 12 pages.
3. Prilepov V., Gasin P., Cirta A., Midoni V., Spoiala D., Ketrush P. Technology of vanadium and its oxides-based nanocomposite structures. *Journal of Optoelectronics and Advanced Materials*, 2014. V. 16, nr. 1-2, p. 232-236.
4. Cîmpeanu, M., Maniu, M., Surugiu, I. *Genetica, metode de studiu*. Iasi: Corson, 2002. 139 p.
5. Luzhna L., Kathiria P., Kovalchuk O. Micronuclei in genotoxicity assessment: from genetics to epigenetics and beyond. *Frontiers in genetics*, 2013. V. 4, art. 131, p. 1-17.

Key words: biological hazards, chromosomes, mitotic index, nanocomposites, toxicity, vanadium oxides.

PARTICIPATION OF THE VITAMIN B COMPLEX IN PROCESSES OF CHEMICAL SELF-PURIFICATION OF THE AQUATIC ENVIRONMENT

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The product sold in pharmacies under the name Vitamin B complex after use can enter surface waters and can participate in various processes of self-purification of water. Photochemical degradation of dissolved substances takes place in the upper layers of water in case of intensive sunlight irradiation. The experimental data obtained indicate that the Vitamin B complex undergoes direct photolysis, so that it is destroyed under the influence of UV rays, with the removal of OH radicals, ensuring increased speeds in the process of photochemical destruction. The effective constant of the direct photolysis has a value $k=12 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and the half-life $\tau=1\text{h } 42 \text{ min } 41\text{s}$. In other words, the studied substrate is very labile and rapidly decomposes photochemically. During photodegradation, the components of the vitamin B complex contribute to the generation of OH radicals in the environment, which is a favorable factor for the development of degradation processes. For example, in the case of direct photolysis of vitamin B₁, which is a component part of the complex, the reaction proceeds as follows:

It has been found that the rate of the induced photochemical oxidation reaction of

vitamin B complex increases with increasing H₂O₂ concentration, the cause being H₂O₂ photolysis and the generation of additional amounts of OH radicals which actively participate in the destruction of Vitamin B complex. The effective constant of the induced photolysis $k=1.27 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and the half-life $\tau=1\text{h } 30 \text{ min } 33 \text{ s}$, which is 12 minutes less compared to the direct photolysis of the complex.

When Cu²⁺ ions are present in the modeling system, they negatively influence the process of destroying the Vitamin B complex, so that the substance stabilizes to form a complex compound with metal ions that are more difficult to destroy. The presence of Cu (II) ions leads to two undesirable consequences: they form a complex compound that is difficult to degrade with the Vitamin B complex; by the formation of these complexes Cu (II) ions are removed from the aquatic environment and thereby diminish the intensity of the photochemical self-purification process.

Therefore, the results obtained indicate that the vitamin B complex actually participates in photochemical self-purification processes of the aquatic environment.

Key words: Cu (II) ions, OH radicals, photolysis, vitamin B, water self-purification.

**NEW SPECIES OF MACROSTELLES (HEMIPTERA,
AUCHENORRHYNCHA) IN THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA**

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The genera *Macrosteles* Fieber, 1866 is included in Tribe Macrostelini Kirkaldi, 1906. The largest genus in this tribe, *Macrosteles*, was established by Fieber (1866) with *Cicada sexnotata* Fallen as its type species. This leafhopper genus contains more than 80 species. The species of the genera *Macrosteles* are distributed in Palaearctic (Europe, Asia, North Africa), Nearctic (USA), Ethiopian (South Africa), Oriental (China, Japan, Taiwan, Korea) regions (Zhang Yalin et al. 2013). Referring to the data of fauna of the Republic of Moldova, there is information about six species: *Macrosteles fieberi* (Edwards, 1889), *M. halophilus* (Horvath, 1903), *M. laevis* (Ribaut, 1927), *M. salsolae* (Puton, 1872), *M. sexnotatus* (Fallen, 1806) and *M. viridigriseus* (Edwards, 1922).

Macrosteles is a difficult and diverse genus, most of its species are similar to each other by external signs, so it is impossible to identify them without dissection. We are using male aedeagus for the exact determination of the species. The representatives of the genus are generally slim insects with dimensions of body about 3-6 mm. The head and the pronotum are usually at the same width.

The research was realized in the northwestern part of the Republic of Moldova at the Scientific Station of Institute of Zoology in Brînzeni commune, Edineț district. The insects were collected in the period from May 25 to September 7 of 2021 in two traps with white and ultraviolet light. During the analysis of them, there were found some of well-known and spread species of genus *Macrosteles*, and also two species, that are new for the fauna: *Macrosteles frontalis* (Scott, 1875), monophage, on *Equisetum palustre* and some other horsetail species and *M. quadripunctulatus* (Kirschbaum, 1868), oliophage, on Asteraceae. The genus *Macrosteles* is important to agriculture as it contains species that feed directly on plant fluids and transmit plant pathogens, as for example *Aster yellows phytoplasma*; also this group of insects is very sensitive to the conditions of environment and reflects the specific characteristics of landscape in detail (Anufriev, 1968). The examined material is deposited in the collection of Museum of Institute of Zoology.

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Key words: *Macrosteles frontalis*, *Macrosteles quadripunctulatus*, determination, Moldovan fauna, new species.

SOME AGROCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF CARBONATE CHERNOZEM AND DIFFERENT SOIL USE

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Soil plays a key role in the functioning of any terrestrial ecosystem. The human impact on soils has sharply increased in the face of increasing intensification of agricultural productions and leads to changes in physical, chemical and biological properties of soils. Therefore, timely control over changes in their properties is very important. The purpose of these studies is to assess changes in the chemical properties of carbonate chernozem under the influence of various types of land use: long-term fertilization, long-term crop rotation, single-crop system, forest belt, fallow.

This research was conducted on the Ketrosoy (Chetrosu) Experimental Station in the Central Zone of Moldova. The soil is a Calcareous chernozem or Calcic chernozem in the World reference base for soil resources with the following characteristics: light loam with 2.5-3.0% humus, the content of mobile phosphate (Machigin) was 0.8-1.5 mg 100 g⁻¹, exchangeable potassium - 18-22 mg 100 g⁻¹ and carbonates - 1.8-2.2% in the 0-20 cm layer. In the experiment, the following variants were studied: 1. long-term fallow (over 30 years); 2. monoculture (winter wheat); 3. crop rotation without fertilization from 1953; 4. crop rotation with mineral fertilizers (N₄₇P₄₆ per year on variants with previous long-term application of N₉₀P₆₀K₆₀); 5. crop rotation with organic fertilizers (manure 18 t ha⁻¹); 6. forest belt. Soil samples were taken from layers 0–20, 20–40, 40–60, 60–80, 80–100 cm in May, the same term for all variants. For each sample, the following agrochemical properties were determined: the content of nitrate nitrogen (NO₃-N), mobile phosphate (P₂O₅) and exchangeable potassium (K₂O).

The highest content of nitrate nitrogen was observed in the variant with minimal anthropogenic impact – with the field protective forest belt. The nitrate nitrogen content in the topsoil (0-20 cm) was minimum in the variant with monoculture – by almost 3.4 times less than in the variant with the forest belt.

Long-term use of crop rotation and organic fertilizers had a favorable effect on the content of mobile phosphorus and exchangeable potassium in the topsoil, but this content sharply decreased in deeper layers.

The lowest content of mobile phosphorus and exchangeable potassium in topsoil was in the variant with monoculture and in the variant with crop rotation and natural soil fertility.

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Key words: carbonate chernozem, chemical properties, crop rotation, mobile phosphorus, nitrate nitrogen content, organic fertilizers.

**THE ASSOCIATIVE AND INVASIVE IMPACT CAUSED BY COMPLEXES
OF PARASITIC INSECTS AND NEMATODES WITH THE APPLICATION
OF CHEMICAL MANAGEMENT IN
MAIZE PLANTATIONS UNDER THE CONDITIONS
OF THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA**

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The main reason why the area cultivated with corn has been expanded in recent years, in the Republic of Moldova, is the high profitability of this crop, taking into account the use of the most modern cultivation technologies in various cultivation systems, the implementation of modern hybrids and integrated protection management. The invasive insect species found on maize plants in their first, vulnerable stages of development, which can cause significant agro-economic impact, are the following: cutworms of the genus *Agrotis* spp., fam. *Elateridae*; Maize leaf weevil – *Tanymecus dilaticollis* Gyll., fam. *Curculionidae*, turnip moth – *Agrotis segetum*, Den. et Sch; cotton bollworm – *Heliothis armigera* Hbn., fam. *Noctuidae*; European corn borer – *Ostrinia nubilalis* Hbn., fam. *Pyraustidae*, ord. *Lepidoptera*. These species are studied annually in association with the parasitic nematode complexes detected on cereal crops, such as the representatives of the order *Tylenchida* consisting of species belonging to the genera: *Pratylenchus*, *Ditylenchus*, *Heterodera*, *Helicotylenchus*, *Paratylenchus*, *Rotylenchus*, *Tylenchorhynchus*, *Merlinius*, *Criconemella* etc., which are also the main pests noticed on maize plants, detected in all areas of phytotechnical cultivation. The attack of these pests is very dangerous when the plants are in the early stages of development (germination – the formation of 3-6 true leaves), when the crop can be completely destroyed, and the economic agents are forced to sow it again. Every year, in the most favorable areas for the established pests, the plants are attacked with varying degrees of frequency and intensity. The chemical treatment of seeds with systemic insecticides was the most effective method of protecting maize against the attack of these pests. Under the specific and unstable climatic conditions of our country, the management of chemical protection of maize provides for the use of all the available technological means to create unfavorable conditions for the development of parasitic agents, namely in the first vegetation period. The aim of this study has been to evaluate the efficacy of two new remedies with systemic insect-nematicidal action: *Curaj*, SC and *Shenzi* 200 SC, in doses of 0.15-0.20 L/ha., in comparison with the untreated control and the standard insecticide *Coragen* 20 SC, 0.20 L/ha., for combating the pest complexes that attack maize and protecting plants in the early stages of vegetation.

The results of the helminth-entomological investigations performed on maize, in the years 2021-2022, present the estimation of the phytosanitary condition of plants in the first stages of growth (germination – 3-6 true leaves), determining the parasitic impact, caused by nematodes and associated invasive insects from soil, compared by zones,

sectors, periods, crop associations and cultivation technologies. The phytosanitary surveys have shown the degree of parasitic impact, by estimating the comparative indices of numerical density (*N.d.*), the following average were obtained: insects – 3-5 individuals/m² and nematodes – 30 individuals/100 g soil, with the prevalence of higher numbers in the Center area (15-20%), in the same research period, conditions caused by climate factors, differentiated by zones. These results served as the basis for mounting research-testing experiments on the new preparations with insecticide-nematicide action: *Curaj SC* and *Shenzi 200 SC* (chlorantraniliprole 200g/kg), as a result of which a biological efficiency of 88-97% was established as compared with the untreated variant. As a result of 3 treatments applied on the complexes of Lepidoptera insects of the family *Noctuidae*, the species *Agrotis segetum*, *Heliothis armigera*, the family *Pyralidae*, the species *Ostrinia nubilalis* associated with the complexes of endoparasitic nematodes of the order *Tylenchida*, the genera *Pratylenchus* and *Ditylenchus*, semi-endoparasitic nematodes of the genera *Heterodera*, *Heterodera* and ectoparasitic nematodes of the genera *Helicotylenchus*, *Paratylenchus*, *Rotylenchus*, *Tylenchorhynchus* and *Merlinius* in the experimental sectors planted with maize, at the Institute of Phytotechny “*Porumbeni*”, Pașcani village, Criuleni district, Central Zone, Republic of Moldova, and the comparative phytosanitary investigations on maize plantations in the growing season in 2021-2022, it was found that, under the agro-climatic conditions of the Republic of Moldova, there were detected 34 harmful organisms and 15 parasitic agents that cause specific diseases, with severe parasitic impact characterized by malformations of roots, stems, leaves and cobs and differ from each other in the degree of frequency and extent, the level of damage to corn crop depending on the area, environmental factors and resistance of the planted hybrids.

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Key words: chemical treatment, efficacy, invasive insect species, maize, nematode, parasitic impact.

**CLIMATE-OPTIMIZED ADAPTIVE-LANDSCAPE TECHNOLOGIES:
CONCEPTUAL-THEORETICAL AND APPLICATIVE SUPPORT**

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The current phase of evolution of arable chernozems in the Carpatho-Danubian Pontic space is characterized by the accelerated development of quantitative-functional changes manifested in interdependent and interdetermined degradation of the organic and structural-aggregate substances system.

Quantitative expression of the level of quantitative-functional degradation is the degree of physical degradation of arable chernozems, which is currently the main factor that determines the meaning of their anthro-po-natural evolution.

Direct causes of quantitative-functional degradation are the profound transformations in the organization and functioning of the soil ecosystem accompanied by the reduction of the total amount of organic substances in the soil, the transformation of soil humic system composition and the amount of organic carbon sequestered and stabilized in structural aggregates. anthro-po-natural chernozemic pedogenesis (metastructuring process).

According to our research, metastructuring is manifested in increasing the degree of clodding and hardsetting of the aggregate structure, compaction of aggregates <5 mm and reduction of their porosity below 40%, reduction of aggregate content 5-1 mm below 50% in the composition of agronomic-valuable structure (0, 25-10 mm), total loss of water stability for aggregates >3 mm.

In the composition of the humic system of the soils is reduced the content of calcium humate responsible for the formation of "chernozem" aggregates (5-1 mm), increases the content of water-soluble humates formed with monovalent cations (Na⁺, K⁺, NH₄⁺). In the composition of fulvic acids, the content of the fractions of "aggressive fulvic substances" increases, leading to the intensification of the mineral transformation processes and the mobilization of the organo-mineral complexes with increased humus content. The changes in the specified humic system contribute to the "eluvial humus losses" of the active agrogenic layer during the wet period of the year. At the same time, the degradation of the aggregate structure leads to a reduction in the degree of physical protection of humus in structural aggregates, intensification of structure degradation due to water action and humus mineralization processes and, respectively, to increased greenhouse gas emissions from arable chernozems. This has led to the establishment of a one-way degrading trend in arable chernozems, accompanied by a significant reduction in the capacity to adapt to climate change and severe climate phenomena, in particular drought, and to an accelerated increase in soil vulnerability to them.

This implied the need to review the paradigm of management of arable chernozem resources by placing emphasis on technological elements capable of restoring the ability to adapt to climate change and reproduce basic agroecosystemic functions: reproductive living modeling, agro-productive.

Their key objectives are:

1. Restoration of the system of organic substances and the humic profile of the soils;

2. Enlarged reproduction of the mass, composition and diversity of soil biota;
3. Restoring the priority role of the process of humus formation and accumulation in the anthropo-natural chernozem pedogenesis;
4. Optimizing the functionality of the pedofunctional system [system of organic substances ↔ structural-aggregate system] responsible for intensifying the processes of enlarged reproduction of chernozem pedogenesis.

More recent research has shown that to these imperatives corresponds the mulch tillage > the minimum tillage system with storage of more than 30% of organic residues at the soil surface (minimum tillage) > direct sowing (no-tillage) .

An important element of these technologies is the practice of bioorganomineral fertilization with products of humic origin.

Monitoring of the structural aggregate state of clayey loamy and clayey chernozems with moderate humus content showed that the administration of bioorganomineral fertilizers in the rhizosphere and in the phyllosphere by foliar treatment contributes, even in years with severe drought, to the establishment in the agrogenic layer of such a structural aggregation that contributes to increasing of the adaptability of arable chernozems to climate change and the severe climate phenomena induced by them.

During the vegetation period, the content of aggregates 5-1 mm is maintained in the range of satisfactory values, thus ensuring the conservation and rational use of evapotranspiration of productive water reserves. In this context, the monitoring of the soil moisture regime showed even in conditions of severe drought at the end of the vegetation period of autumn crops (wheat, barley, rapeseed) the water content in the agrogenic layer is 0.45-0.52 FC (*Field Capacity*).

Acknowledgments: The researches were carried out within the Technology Transfer Project 21.80015.58.07.253T

Key words: bioorganomineral fertilization, chernozems, calcium humate, fulvic acids, humus mineralization, quantitative-functional degradation.

**FOSSIL FELIDAE (GENUS *METAILURUS*) IN THE MIOCENE
OF THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA**

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Fossil Felidae of the genus *Metailurus* are widely known in Miocene deposits of Eurasia and Africa and were part of the Hipparion faunas of Vallesia and Turoly.

The earliest finds of fossil *Metailurus* in the Republic of Moldova are known from the Vallesian Hipparion fauna of Calfa (Middle Sarmatian, Calfin faunal complex, MN9; 12.0-10.8 Ma) - *Metailurus pamiri* (Ozansoy, 1965). The material is represented by the right branch of the lower jaw of the juvenile with dp3-dp4, m1, and alveolus p2, as well as isolated teeth and postcranial skeleton bones. *Metailurus cf. parvulus* Hensel 1862, a characteristic species for the hipparion faunas of the Late Sarmatian (locality of Poksesti, Poksesti faunal complex, MN 10.7-8.7 Ma) and Meotis (Early to Middle Turonian) appears in Late Vallesian. Fossil material was found during excavations in Poksesti in 2012 and is represented by a complete lower jaw of an adult.

Metailurus cf. parvulus is known from a number of localities of hipparion faunas of Meotis: *M. cf. parvulus* (= *Machairodus schlosseri* Weith.) from a locality near Cimislia (MN 12; 8.0 Ma) and *M. parvulus* (= *Machairodus parvulus* Hens.) from a locality near Taraclia (MN 12; 8.0 Ma).

In the Early Pliocene the composition of faunal complexes significantly changes and the semi-sabre-toothed Felidae of the genus *Metailurus* are replaced by representatives of the genus *Dinofelis*, found in a number of localities of Pliocene age of the Republic of Moldova.

Acknowledgments: The studies were performed within the State Program project 20.80009.7007.02 and doctoral project: "Terrestrial carnivorous mammals (Mammalia: Carnivora) from the Miocene of the Republic of Moldova".

Key words: hipparion faunas, *Metailurus pamiri*, *Metailurus cf. parvulus*, Miocene deposits, the change of faunal complexes.

**CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE STUDY OF THE ANTS (INSECTS:
FORMICIDAE) FROM THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA**

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The research was carried out in the districts of Chisinau, Calarasi, Anenii Noi, Comrat and Gagauzia in 2022. 3 types of ants were identified - *Lasius*, *Formica* and *Camponotus*. The collections were made in different habitats such as alfalfa field or with other crops, meadow in the forest or forest or river bank. Dependence on the area and the identified ant species was observed. Species of the genus *Camponotus* ants were identified only in samples collected from central Moldova (Calarasi). Habitat dependence and the species identified in the sample collected from this habitat were observed. The species *Lasius alienus* and a species of the genus *Formica* have been identified in the alfalfa plains. *Lasius emarginatus*, being a forest species, was also identified only in the samples collected from this habitat.

Acknowledgments: The study was supported by the project 220.80009.7007.02

Key words: *Formica*, *Lasius alienus*, *Lasius emarginatus*, ants species, habitat dependence.

DEVELOPMENT OF A MATHEMATICAL MODELS SYSTEM FOR REMOTE ASSESSMENT SOIL EROSION

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The purpose of the study is developing a system for remote monitoring of the degree of soil erosion in winter wheat field crops.

For identification eroded soils was used an indicator approach, based on the sensitivity of winter wheat crop to soil erosivity. The assessment of winter wheat crops conditions was carried out according to the data of vegetation index NDVI.

The system of mathematical models developed for winter wheat production crops, based on the NDVI, is adequate and has a high information capacity. The obtained mathematical models were applied on the lands of the central part of the Grigoriopol district occupied in the period 2017-2021 by winter wheat crops grouped by the vegetation index NDVI. As a result, on an area of 16,490 hectares, the soils erosivity was determined by remote data (fig).

Fig. Remote estimation of soils erosivity on the lands of the central part of the Grigoriopol district

Remote estimation of soils erosivity based on the proposed system of equations better corresponds to the data of field studies of soil power compared with the data of soil maps of scale 1:50 000 and 1:10 000 and the results of soil erosion modeling by the RUSLE method.

The system of mathematical models there has been developed can be used for preliminary assessment of the degree of soil erosivity, to facilitate the work of soil scientists during soil survey.

Key words: mathematical models, remote monitoring, soil erosion, vegetation index NDVI, wheat field crops.

BAT FAUNA (MAMMALIA, CHIROPTERA) FROM LIMESTONE MINES OF MOLOVATA NOUĂ

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The limestone mines of Molovata Nouă are located on the left bank of Nistru river (47.32 N, 29.08 E) at a distance of about 200 m from the river and at an altitude of 70 m. There are 8 entrances about the same size of 4-6 m wide and 3-3.5 m high. The corridors extend on a distance of over 700 m and are parallel, descending downwards. The ceiling and the walls have multiple cracks of 4-10 cm wide and 5-15 cm depth left after machine excavation, where the bats find shelter. This site was studied for the first time, it was not mentioned before in the literature. In the period 2020-2021 the site was visited three times: in September 2020, at the end of hibernation period in March 2021 and in June 2021. The bats were studied directly by visual observations, all observed individuals were identified.

In all the periods 11 bat species from two families were registered: *Rhinolophus hipposideros* from fam. Rhinolophidae, *Myotis myotis*, *M. blythii*, *M. daubentonii*, *M. dasynceme*, *M. nattereri*, *M. bechsteinii*, *M. mystacinus*, *Eptesicus serotinus*, *Plecotus auritus* and *P. austriacus* from fam. Vespertilionidae. The species abundance was different depending on the season. In September, when the bats are actively feeding and gather in underground sites for hibernation, 397 individuals from 9 species were recorded, dominant being *M. daubentonii* (43.94%), followed by *E. serotinus* (25.25%) and *M. mystacinus* (23.99%). Other species were observed in low amount, between 0.25% and 3.03%, while the species *M. nattereri* and *M. bechsteinii* were not registered. At the end of hibernation period the bat diversity and number were the highest – 10 species with 478 individuals, which shows the suitability of the site for many species hibernation. The dominant species was *M. daubentonii*, representing more than half of bat community, followed by *R. hipposideros* (17.15%) and *M. myotis* (15.48%), while other species had a low percent and *M. blythii* was not observed. In June, when reproduction occurs, no maternity colony was found and the bats visited the site only for daytime rest. The bat fauna was represented by 59 individuals from 6 species (*M. myotis*, *M. daubentonii*, *M. dasynceme*, *E. serotinus*, *P. auritus* and *P. austriacus*), dominant being *M. daubentonii* with more than 76%, and the rest of the species had the abundance of 1.69% to 8.47%.

All the species, except *E. serotinus*, are listed in the Red book of the Republic of Moldova. At European level all species are listed in Appendix II of Bern Convention and in Annex II of Convention on the Protection of Migratory Species. We have to mention the presence in rather large number (91 individuals) of critically endangered species *M. myotis* that was not registered in the last 50 years. The species *M. nattereri* (CR) was recorded at hibernation in low number for the first time in the last 30 years and *M. bechsteinii* (CR) was previously registered only in Cricova and Goianul Nou mines from the central part of the republic.

The Molovata Noua limestone mines represent an important site for bat diversity conservation in Moldova and the monitoring of bat fauna will continue.

Acknowledgments: The studies were performed within the State Program project 20.80009.7007.02.

Key words: *Rhinolophidae*, *Vespertilionidae*, bat fauna, limestone mines, monitoring, species abundance.

TROPHIC SPECTRUM OF THE LONG-EARED OWL (*ASIO OTUS*) IN THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA

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The long-eared owl (*Asio otus*) is a sedentary bird in Moldova and one of the most widespread in Europe. The trophic spectrum of *A. otus* was established during the winter and nesting periods in different regions of the Republic of Moldova in the period 2009-2022. During the digestion process the owl regurgitates the undigested rests of eaten animals (bones, fur, feathers, insect chitin etc.) as pellets. The study of the pellets provides important data concerning the diet of prey birds, the small mammal fauna in the area, the density of small mammal species, their spreading etc. The small mammals and bat species were identified after the dentition, maxillary and mandibular bones.

In the northern area (Volodeni locality, Edineț district) the trophic spectrum of *A. otus* during the winter period consists only of rodent species. The field voles (genus *Microtus*) were dominant with over 70%, followed by the species genus *Apodemus* with 12.66%, *A. agrarius* with 7.59% and *Mus* species with 5.07%.

In Unguri village (Ocnița district) the trophic spectrum of the long-eared owl in nesting period also consisted only of rodents. The most abundant were the *Microtus* genus species, constituting 73.02%. *Mus* genus species constituted 11.11%, the three species of *Apodemus* genus constituted about 15%, the dominant being *A. sylvaticus* with 8.73%, and *Muscardinus avellanarius* with less than 1%. In the urban ecosystems of Chisinau, the trophic spectrum of the *A. otus* was much more diverse and consisted of mammals of three orders (Soricomorpha, Chiroptera, Rodentia) and birds, of which the share of shrews was 0.81%, of bats – 0.2%, of birds – 2.55%, while the main trophic objects were the rodents - over 95%. The *Microtus* species dominated with 70.99%, followed the *Mus* species with 10.88% and *A. sylvaticus* with 10.34%. Other species of the genus *Apodemus* accumulated less than 4%. *M. avellanarius* and *R. norvegicus* had a share of only 0.13%. Among other mammal groups in the diet of long-eared owl from Chisinau representatives of shrews and bats have been registered in very low percent. The shrews were represented by 4 species (*Crocidura suaveolens*, *C. leucodon*, *Sorex minutus*, *S. araneus*) and the bats – by 2 species (*Eptesicus serotinus* and *Vespertilio murinus*).

In the Sadaclia village (Basarabasca district) from the southern part of the republic in the pellets mammals of the orders Soricomorpha, Rodentia and birds were identified. The dominant species were the field voles (*Microtus*), which represented more than half of identified animals, followed by the *Apodemus* species with 19.71%, and *Mus* species with 16.42%. Other species had a lower percent: *A. agrarius* (2.55%), *Rattus norvegicus* (0.73%) and *Muscardinus avellanarius* (0.37%). The birds had a rather high proportion – 9.49%, while the shrews, represented by one species *C. leucodon* – only 0.37%.

Many rodent species are important pests to agriculture. The long-eared owl is a predator that exerts constant pressure on rodent density, thus regulating their number.

Acknowledgments: The studies were performed within the State Program project 20.80009.7007.02.

Key words: *Asio otus*, undigested rests, trophic spectrum, urban ecosystems.

THE BIOECOLOGICAL SPECTRUM OF HERBACEOUS SPECIES IN THE CENTER OF BALTI CITY

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The intensification of the processes in which permanent morphological changes of the soil cover take place has led to the need for the floristic study of the urban ecosystems. The study of the floristic diversity in the square in the center of Balti city, next to the bell tower, is of major scientific interest as it is a rather anthropized and crowded place. In the limit of the researched resort were registered 41 herbaceous species, belonging to 37 genera, grouped in 21 families. The degree of coverage is 95 - 100%. It is dominated by the Poaceae and Asteraceae families, being represented by a number of 9 and 7 species. Among the dominant species are: *Arctium lappa* L., *Lolium perenne* L., *Setaria viridis* (L.) Beauv., *S. glauca* (L.) Beauv., *Elytrigia repens* L., *Hordeum murinum* L., *Amaranthus retroflexus* L., *Poa bulbosa* L., *Cirsium arvense* L. Scop., *C. serrulatum* (Bieb.) Fisch. They constitute about 90% of the surface of the vegetal carpet. Although in the city center, including in this sector, maintenance works is periodically carried out, the flora remains fairly constant. This is due to the fact that the mentioned plants largely combine vegetative and seed reproduction, which contributes to their distribution and renewal in areas exposed to the impact of the anthropogenic factor.

The presence of two invasive species was attested within the resort: *Erigeron annuus* (L.) Pers and *Humulus lupulus* L. Their ability to adapt and multiply is quite high and as a result could contribute to the elimination of spontaneous flora species, which is represented by 18% of all species. The high share of ruderal (56%) and segetal - ruderal (26%) groups represents an index of the significant anthropogenic load on the vegetation of the study area.

In relation to the humidity conditions, the greatest diversity of the flora is represented by mesophytes - 27%, xeromesophytes, mesophytes - 27%, as well as xeromesophytes - 19%. The share of groups that require a high humidity regime is quite small.

In relation to the trophicity of the substrate, 18 indicator species were identified: Eutrophic - 14 species (78% of the total); Megatrophic - a species (5% of the total); Eutrophic, Mesotrophic - 2 species (11% of the total); Mesotrophic, Eutrophic - a species (6% of the total).

The analysis of the geobotanical spectrum shows us that the species in this resort have various centers of origin. Taxas of Eurasian and Cosmopolitan origin account for 33%, these being represented by 12 species each. Centers of origin: Circumpolar - is represented by 3 species (8% of the total); North America - 2 species (5% of the total); the other centers of origin are represented by a single species.

The floristic study shows us that the flora of the Balti urban ecosystem was formed as a result of the preservation of native spontaneous species, as well as the penetration of non-native species, in different ways on the territory of the country.

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Key words: anthropized place, floristic diversity, invasive species, spontaneous species, urban ecosystems.

**ATMOSPHERIC BREAKDOWN CHEMISTRY OF
THE NEW GREEN SOLVENT 2,2,5,5- TETRAMETHYLOXOLANE:
GAS-PHASE RATE CONSTANTS EVALUATION TOWARDS OH AND CL
RADICALS AT 298 K AND 1 BAR**

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Aromatic solvents, unsustainably sourced from the petroleum industry, are harmful to health, often potentially carcinogenic, and environmentally hazardous [1]. Considerable research effort therefore has been directed towards developing less harmful and hazardous new "green" solvents. Such a promising green solvent with unusual properties is 2,2,5,5-tetramethylloxolane (TMO) [2]. In the present study the gas-phase reactivity of TMO towards OH radicals and Cl atoms at temperature of 296 K and total pressure on 1 bar of synthetic air was investigated using the ESC-Q-UAIC (Environmental Simulation Chamber made of quartz from "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iasi) chamber facilities [3]. Results obtained from the relative kinetic studies showed the following rate constants: $k_{(TMO+OH)} = (3.1 \pm 0.4) \times 10^{-12}$ cm³molecule⁻¹s⁻¹ and $k_{(TMO+Cl)} = (1.2 \pm 0.1) \times 10^{-10}$ cm³molecule⁻¹s⁻¹. Kinetic data are compared with structure-activity-relationship estimated values. Possible atmospheric implications for TMO use as a new "green" solvent are highlighted in the present study.

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References:

1. Jimenez-Gonzalez, C., Ponder, C. S., Broxterman, Q. B., and Manley, J. B.: Using the Right Green Yardstick: Why Process Mass Intensity Is Used in the Pharmaceutical Industry To Drive More Sustainable Processes, *Org. Process Res. Dev.*, 15, 912-917, 10.1021/op200097d, 2011.
2. Byrne, F., Forier, B., Bossaert, G., Hoebers, C., Farmer, T. J., Clark, J. H., and Hunt, A. J.: 2,2,5,5- Tetramethyltetrahydrofuran (TMTHF): a non-polar, non-peroxide forming ether replacement for hazardous hydrocarbon solvents, *Green Chem.*, 19, 3671-3678, 10.1039/C7GC01392B, 2017.
3. Roman, C., Arsene, C., Bejan, I. G., and Olariu, R. I.: Investigations into the gas-phase photolysis and OH radical kinetics of nitrocatechols: implications of intramolecular interactions on their atmospheric behaviour, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 22, 2203-2219, 10.5194/acp-22-2203-2022, 2022.

Key words: aromatic solvents, constants evaluation, the environmental hazards, new "green" solvents, ESC-Q-UAIC.

**APPLICATION OF BIOTECHNICAL STRUCTURES TO
IMPROVE BREEDING CONDITIONS OF WETLAND BIRDS
IN THE YAGORLYK NATURE RESERVE**

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In conditions of unstable hydrological regime of the Dniester River, which is expressed in frequent, non-cyclical fluctuations of the water level, of great importance is the improvement of nesting conditions for wetland birds. In 2021, in accordance with the recommendations of the Reconstruction and Management Plan for the Yagorlyk Nature Reserve 4 nesting rafts were created, the target species are Great Crested Grebe and Ferruginous Duck. Rafts about 1.5 m across are made of planks and wooden slats, or from plastic containers, wire mesh and turf. A load serving as an anchor is tied to the bottom of the rafts with a rope. In the spring of 2022, 15 closed-type platforms for nesting wetland birds were also manufactured and installed among the hydrophytes. The platforms were made of wooden pallets, for buoyancy, foam material "penoplex" and plastic containers were placed under the platform. A pipe made of metal mesh and meadow hay was fixed to the platform. The dimensions of the platforms are 100/60 cm, the size of the nest tube is 80 cm in length and 30 cm in inner diameter. When nesting sites are located in dense thickets of wetland vegetation, all plants around the nest are removed by 30-40cm. The nests were located in two groups at a distance of 10 – 20 meters from each other: 1 group of 5 nests in the area of the tract "Balta"; 2 group of 10 nests in the Goyan Bay near the village of Doybany. The platforms were installed in March, immediately after the ice meltdown.

In addition to the above target species, such artificial rafts will be used by Coots and other waterfowl. Using the experience of creating biotechnical structures in conditions of unstable hydrological regime of the Dniester River it will allow to preserve and improve habitats for a vulnerable group of birds of the middle and lower Dniester in the future. Monitoring of the ornithopopulation of limnophiles it will allow tracking the dynamics of changes in the fauna of birds of the middle and lower Dniester and to identify species that are particularly vulnerable to which it is urgently necessary to apply biotechnical methods.

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References:

Грищенко В.Н. Биотехнические мероприятия по охране редких видов птиц. Черновцы, 1997. 143 с.

Заповедник «Ягорлык». План реконструкции и управления как путь сохранения биологического разнообразия /Шабанова Г.А., Изверская, Т.Д., Гендов В.С., Сыродоев Г.Н. [и др.], под науч. ред. Г.А. Шабановой. Дубоссары: Эсо-Тирас, 2011. 128 с.

Key words: Middle and lower Dniester, nesting conditions, platforms for nesting, water level fluctuations, wetland birds.

GROWTH CHARACTERISTICS OF FUNGAL PATHOGENS IN CONDITIONS OF WATER RESTRICTIONS

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The increased impact of climate change on plant ecosystems and the security of water resources causes the prevalence of the complex fungal diseases, associated with root and stem rot, seedling rot in the early stage of growth, leaf spot, but also black embryo (black point) in mature seeds. The diversity of these diseases presents a major impediment to achieving the productive potential of the wheat globally. This research focuses on the behavior of causative agents of necrosis under water restriction conditions.

Some cultural and morphological characters of 3 strains of *Drechslera sorokiniana*, *Fusarium solani* and *Alternaria alternata* species on the osmotically modified Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) environment were investigated. Water restrictions were adjusted with polyethylene glycol (PEG 6000) in concentrations of 5%, 10% and 20% from the volume. PDA boards, inoculated in the center with discs of uniform size (5 mm) were incubated for 7 days at a temperature of 25°C. The indices of radial growth of the colony, the texture of the aerial mycelium, the surface and reverse color, the intensity of pigmentation and the zoning were recorded on the 4th and 7th days after the initiation of the culture. The fungi *F. solani*, *A. alternata* and *D. sorokiniana* revealed, respectively, a major, medium and low growth rate over the entire 7-day interval. The radial growth of the mycelium varied in a wide range, the growth rate being more pronounced in the period 1-4 days after the initiation of the culture. The water restrictions established at the administration of PEG 6000 in 20% concentration produced significant inhibition of *F. solani* growth, but also *A. alternata* in the period of 5-7 days from the initiation of culture. The mycelium *D. sorokiniana* was tested with the most advantageous increase in various drought simulations in relation to the control. The analysis of the growth rate variance of *F. solani* mycelium demonstrated a considerable decrease in the share of the fungal strain factor (68.9%-17.0%), instead increasing the contribution of PEG 6000 concentration in the 7-day culture (18.0%-48.3%). The high level of PEG 6000 was a decisive factor for the growth of *D. sorokiniana* strains (76.5%-93.6%). The decrease in the weight of the PEG 6000 factor was accompanied by the increase of the weight fungal strain equally in the case of the growth rate of the *A. alternata* fungus. In simulated drought conditions at the administration of PEG 6000, it has been revealed the spread of the mycelium in the form of a dense submerged plate or stretched film. At the same time, the delayed appearance of the aerial mycelium, the increase or decrease of the pigmentation intensity of the mycelium, the lack or decrease of the border band show the adaptability of the growth to the water restrictions.

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Key words: climate change, drought simulations, fungal diseases, necrosis, radial growth.

**THE IMPACT OF REGIONAL CLIMATE CHANGE ON THE
SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR IN
THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA**

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In the last two decades, the sustainable development of agriculture in the Republic of Moldova is increasingly addressed both in academic debates and in farmers' associations. The mutual support of these parties directly involved in current research on the one hand and practice on the other are strategic elements in identifying the essential needs of the population, connected to the technological limits on the ability to meet the needs of the present and the future.

Socio-cultural development, political stability, economic growth, and the implementation of effective strategies are needed by the agricultural sector at present, to bring the main branch of development of countries according to high standards in the field of production efficiency.

Efficient management of agro-climatic resources in the context of regional climate change is becoming an important condition for knowing the impact of significant weather and climate risks on the agricultural sector.

Thus, in the context of regional climate change it is important to observe and implement effective measures in the agricultural sector, effectively managing agro-climatic resources in terms of researched meteorological and climate risks, namely: drought, vegetation frosts, torrential and heavy rains, and hail massive.

At present, the socio-economic costs of natural disasters associated with climate change such as those listed above are significant. According to researchers, it is assumed that both their intensity and frequency will increase significantly in the future, which is mainly determined by climate change. The consequences of recent events have been disastrous. As an example, only the droughts of 2007, 2012, 2015, and 2020 caused significant direct losses, estimated at about 1.0-1.25 billion US dollars each.

Recent studies show that climate change is affecting all regions of the world and if extreme weather events and rainfall are becoming more frequent on the other side we are facing extreme heat waves and drought.

The analysis of the potential impact of climate change on the sustainable development of the agricultural sector in the Republic of Moldova is of enormous interest for knowing the mechanism of manifestation of these risks in order to reduce the negative effects.

Key words: agro-climatic resources, climate risks, regional climate change, significant direct losses.

**GEOPAEDOLOGICAL INVESTIGATIONS AT THE ARCHAEOLOGICAL
SITE LIPOVENI II-LA NISIPĂRIE
FROM CIMISLIA DISTRICT**

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The archaeological site Lipoveni II-*La nisipărie* is located in the suburbs of the Lipoveni village from Cimișlia district. The analyzed soil samples were taken from the archaeological section in the year 2021. The investigated soil is a typical uncovered chernozem and, according to the granulometric composition, it is characterized as loamy-sandy on the loamy sand's parental rock. For comparison, soil samples were also collected from arable land, at a distance of 100 m from the archaeological site, up to the depth of the parent rock of 130 cm, on the loam's parental rock. The density of solid phase of the samples collected from the site, determined according to Petinov method, constitutes 2,53-2,56 g/cm³ up to a depth of 150 cm and 2,57-2,65 g/cm³ in the underlying horizons. The values of apparent density do not correspond to a natural genetic profile, especially from 60 cm in depth. The parameters of density of the solid phase of control profile (from arable land) was in accordance with the genetic regularities of an intact soil profile. The density of the solid phase correlates with the content of humus (organic matter) in the soil. The humus was determined using the method of I. V. Tiurin, based on the oxidation of organic carbon (C_{org}), with the modifications proposed by V. N. Simakov. The humus content on the entire site profile was high (2,93-4,00 %) in the upper horizons and 2,40-3,67 % in the underlying ones, correspondingly the C_{org} content also was increased. This argues for the low values of the solid phase density in the underlying horizons. For the first half meter depth, that is in the upper horizons, the humus content corresponds to this type of soil [1]. In the same time, the high content of humus and C_{org} in the underlying horizons could be originated from anthropic activity. Regarding the granulometric composition, analyzed by the pipette method of N. A. Kacinskii [2], we note the small content of fine clay (< 0,001 mm) on the site profile, the values ranging between 6,27-10,40 % in the upper horizons and 4,49-8,73 % in the underlying ones. The high content of the sand fraction (56,12-77,34 %) is due to the parent rock on which the given soil was formed – loamy sand. Special attention is paid to the segmentation of the profile into four layers: I. 0-60 cm, which according to determined parameters corresponds with the control profile from the arable land (that is to say an integral profile); the other layers show traces of human activity; layer II. 60-120 cm, with frequent presence of burnt charcoal; layer III. 120-140 cm and layer IV. 140-200 cm.

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References:

1. Cerbari V. *Monitoringul calității solurilor Republicii Moldova [The Republic of Moldova's soils quality monitoring]*. Chișinău: Pontos, 2010, p. 121.
2. Jigău Gh., Nagacevschi T. *Ghid al disciplinei Fizica Solului [Guide of the Soil Physics discipline]*. Chișinău: CEP USM, 2006

Key words: human activity, humus content, parameters of soil, solid phase density, uncovered chernozem.

ELEMENTS OF AGROGENIC EVOLUTION OF THE AGGREGATIC STRUCTURE OF CLAYEY-LOAMY AND LOAMY-CLAYEY MODERATE HUMIFERUS CHERNOZEMS

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The aggregate structure of soils is a distinct feature by which they differ from other bioroutinar systems and materialize in their eco/agroecosystemic functions. Through this prism of ideas, chernozems differ from other types of soils by the “chernozemic structure” represented by aggregates with dimensions mainly between 5-1 mm, porous and with increased water stability. Its formation and dynamics in conditions of natural ecosystems is the product of the interdependent and interdetermined interaction of coagulation, coprolitic and root mechanisms of aggregation-structuring that ensure the reproduction-renewal of the "chernozem structure" during the vegetation period thus ensuring the adaptation of ecosystems to the dynamics of environmental conditions.

Therefore, during the vegetation period, the content of valuable agronomic aggregates (0.25-10 mm) and agronomically precious ones (5-1 mm) are maintained in the optimal value ranges, respectively 70-80% and 50-60%. The content of aggregates > 10 mm during the vegetation varies insignificantly, and that of the aggregates <0.25 mm does not exceed 4%.

In such a dynamic, chernozems have a great ability to adapt to environmental conditions, including climate change, especially to drought.

In agroecosystem conditions, the intensity of the reproduction-renewal mechanisms of the “chernozem structure” is significantly reduced and the decisive role in the dynamics of structural composition belongs to the thermo-compression mechanism determined by the alternation of the hydrothermal regime of arable chernozems.

In the agrogenic layer, the “agrogenic structuring” leads to the increase of the aggregates content >10 mm and of the 5-10 mm ones. Their content increases during the growing season with maximum values at the end of it. The content of 5-1 mm aggregates during the vegetation period is reduced from 50-53% to 43-40% in the arable layer and below 35% in the subarable layer.

In the transition horizon (B) the structuring process is mainly determined by the thermo-compressive mechanism and leads to the formation of aggregates >7 mm, their content at the end of the vegetation period has values higher than 60%.

Significantly reduces soil aggregate stability. In the arable layer (0-20-25 cm) the aggregates >3 mm have no water stability. Aggregates 2-1 and 1-0.5 mm are characterized by maximum water stability. The aggregate content <0.25 mm is greater than 50%.

In the subarable layer, the water stability of the 5-3 mm aggregates slightly increases due to their partial compaction and the reduction of the mesopore volume. At the same time, however, it is due to the compaction of 5-3 mm aggregates and the reduction of the volume of aggregate pores. At the same time in the subarable layer aggregates with dimensions >10 mm with morphological and physical features not characteristic of chernozems are formed. The subarable layer is characterized by rigid placement of structural aggregates in the subarable layer in the wet period of the year creates anaerobic

conditions with negative impact on the soil biota, at the same time due to the reduction of the volume of interaggregate pores is the formation of an anisotropic profile of the porous space. This leads to a reduction in hydraulic conductivity on the soil profile and involves the seasonal over-wetting of arable chernozems during the wet period of the year.

Under conditions of low water stability of the structure, the degree of physical protection of organic carbon is reduced and as a result increase CO₂ emissions from soils. It also increases vulnerability to drought.

More recent research has shown that in order to ensure the stability of the structural-aggregate state during the vegetation period, measures are necessary to intensify the activity of the soil biota. Their number includes the treatment of soils with algal preparations based on nitrogen-fixing cyanophyte algae.

Their application to the soil in the early phases of the vegetation period contributes to the intensification of the coagulation, -radicular and coprolitic aggregation-structuring mechanisms of the soil mass with the formation of 7-1 mm aggregates and the increase of the content of water stable aggregates with a diameter of 7-1 mm. The monitoring of the structural aggregate condition during the vegetation period showed that the nitrogen-fixing cyanophyte algaeflora contributes to the modeling of the soil biopedoplasm with the formation of a favorable environment for the functioning of the soil biome.

The maximum effects were found in the *Nostoc gelatinosum* variant (3 l / ha) in sunflower and corn crops.

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Key words: agronomic aggregates, chernozems, cyanophyte algae, hydrothermal regime, structure of soils.

CLIMATE INFLUENCES ON THE LANDSCAPES OF THE NARNOVA HYDROGRAPHIC BASIN

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Landscape structure and function can change for many reasons and in many ways. Change in a patch or a landscape can be caused by any number of factors. Some of these are intrinsic, other causes are extrinsic to the ecosystem and are imposed by outside forces, such as climate change and disturbance events. The potential causes of change may be interrelated in complex ways. A drought may make a forest more vulnerable to pathogens or a new clearing may increase the vulnerability of adjacent trees to windthrow. Global climate change will force many species to adjust their geographical distributions in the near future, with important consequences for biodiversity, conservation biology and ecosystem services. Changes in landscape structure can have several spatial and temporal forms. Patches can shrink or expand, or be lost entirely. Successional dynamics on patches can lead to a shifting mosaic of patch types through time. Some changes are nearly instantaneous and occur over very short periods of time, such as the effect of fire. Other changes occur slowly and take a longer period of time to develop, such as desertification. Patch configuration on a landscape can also change. Patches can become perforated by other patch types, and large patches can be fragmented into several smaller patches.

The varied natural conditions of the Nârnova river basin, with varying altitudes, have determined the presence of a wide variety of land categories (types of landscapes). Climatic conditions have had a direct influence on the increase and decrease of certain areas of land. Within the Nârnova river basin, during the years 1991-2020, an average temperature of 10.88 degrees C was registered, and the average rainfall was 580 mm. Recently, a series of hydroclimatic changes have appeared that have led to the reduction of the snow layer, the change of precipitation from snow type to rain. Drought phenomena have also become more numerous, which has further led to the appearance of vegetation fires (dry vegetation has become more flammable) as the climate grows warmer and drier. Within the Narnova river basin, the arid climate has led to a decrease in the number and surface of the lakes, which has directly influenced even the actual course of the river, decreasing its flow. The surface of many perennial landscapes has turned into agricultural or pasture landscapes. The latitudinal distribution of temperatures influenced the growth of forest and multiannual landscapes. The torrential rains also intensified, which led to intense soil erosion due to the rather rugged terrain. This in turn led to the transition from arable landscapes to shrubs, bushes, eroded pastures, etc. If climate change is affecting landscape processes over the multidecadal time scales of human lives and infrastructure design, that could have major implications for human health and safety, economic stability, water security, natural-resource management, and ecosystem resilience.

Key words: causes of change, drought, landscape structure, climatic conditions

**EX-SITU AND IN-VITRO PROPAGATION OF
GENISTA TETRAGONA IN REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA**

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Botanic gardens are the main institutions involved in *ex situ* conservation of wild plant diversity and have adopted the Target 8 of the Global Strategy for Plant Conservation (GSPC), which evokes that 75% of threatened plant species should be maintained in *ex situ* collections in order to provide genetic diversity for ecological restoration efforts.

The *ex situ* population of *Genista tetragona* Besser (Fabaceae) was created in 2000 by transplanting several vegetative specimens from the natural habitat (the vicinity of vill. Mașcăuți, Criuleni district) to the experimental plot of rare plants (National Botanical Garden (Institute), Chișinău), in order to continue on *in situ* restoration programs. The plants took root on the site, but during 2000-21 they did not form seeds, and efforts for vegetative propagation did not produce results. As a result, in 2021-22 actions were taken to propagate this species by microclonal methods. *Genista tetragona* is a xerophyllous, calciphylous shrub species. Blooms in April-May and fructifies in June-August. In the Republic of Moldova species grows in the districts of Camenca, Rîbnița, Dubăsari, Grigoriopol and Orhei. It is a Podolian endemic, a tertiary relict. It is a highly decorative shrub, especially in the spring time. The species is protected globally – included in the IUCN Red list of threatened species, Annexes of Bern Convention, and regionally – protected by state in the Republic of Moldova and included in the Red Book of the republic and Ukraine.

At present, priority propagation is given to *in vitro* techniques that offer wide opportunities in the conservation of rare and endangered plant species, thus being a complementary to *in situ* conservation.

This study aimed at the introduction and multiplication in the *in vitro* culture of the species *Genista tetragona*. *In vitro* sampling, inoculation and culture methods were traditional. The MS medium (Murashige, Skoog, 1962), supplemented with BAP and TDZ cytokines (0.5 mg/l), served as the basic nutrient substrate. Apical bud segments were used as biological material. The inoculated material under aseptic conditions was transferred to the culture chamber with a specific regime for the investigated plants. In the process of *in vitro* cultivation, observations and analyzes were performed in order to microclon them. Phytohormones had different effects on the development of shoots and on the rate of seedling proliferation *in vitro*. Maximum proliferation values were obtained on the medium supplemented with BAP of 10.4 vigorous new shoots/explant, TDZ generated some symptoms of hyperhydration. *In vitro* seedlings are currently being induced to take root.

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Key words: *Genista tetragona*, microclonal methods, *ex situ* conservation, *in vitro* techniques, propagation.

THE INFLUENCE OF TOMATIN BAC ON THE PROCESS OF ALCOHOLIC FERMENTATION OF WASTE BIOMAS

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The quantity of agricultural waste has been rising rapidly all over the world, many studies has revealed that fruits and vegetables are the main source of bioactive compounds; in most cases, wastes and byproducts generated by the food processing industry present similar or a higher content of antioxidant compounds. Therefore, there is an increasing interest in finding new ways for their processing toward safely upgrading these wastes for recovering high-value-added products with a sustainable approach. Among food waste, the abundance of bioactive compounds in byproducts derived from tomato suggests possibility of utilizing them as a low-cost source of antioxidants as functional ingredients. The solid residue remaining after the industrial processing of tomatoes (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.), tomato pomace, consists of large amounts of tomato peels and seeds that currently find use as animal feed and fertilizers or are sent to landfill. However, it is still rich in important antioxidant present in the ripened tomato. In this line, numerous approaches have been proposed for the valorization of the unused parts of tomato in various sectors.

In the past, people added these byproducts as compost to the soil for agricultural purposes, thus allowing the recycling of nutrients. Today, instead, because of the huge increase in the accumulation of large amounts of waste matter, reducing waste is among the efforts to relieve the pressure on natural resources and move toward more sustainable food systems. So, a critical and up-to-date review has been conducted on the latest individual valorization technologies aimed at the generation of value-added by-products from industrial food wastes. Waste treatment in wine and alcohol industry is a current problem in Republic of Moldova. The annual volumes of the production and accumulation of liquid wastes are considerable.

The aim of the scientific research is to examine the associated advantages and drawbacks of each technique separately along with the assessment of process parameters affecting the efficiency of the generation of the bio-based products. Research of the influence of tomatine BAC on the process of alcoholic fermentation in the laboratory conditions. The biomass used was the waste from the ethyl alcohol production "GARMA GRUP" L.L.C. company. The testing of tomatine BAC was performed in order to explore possible activating or inhibiting effect on the alcoholic fermentation process.

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Key words: agricultural waste, alcoholic fermentation, antioxidants, sustainable approach, tomato pomace, valorisation.

FIXED SOURCES OF ATMOSPHERIC AIR POLLUTION IN THE BALTI URBAN ECOSYSTEM

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Stationary sources of pollution (excluding the household sector) in the Balti urban ecosystem eliminate a huge volume of pollutants into the atmosphere. The number of economic agents registered in the municipality that eliminate pollutants in the atmosphere in the production process for the period 2014 - 2021 is decreasing: from 408 to 222. The dynamics of the volume of emissions in the municipality is increasing for the period 2014-2021 from 855.13 t to 1544.86 t. (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 The dynamics of the volume of emissions from stationary sources in Balti municipality (2014 - 2021)

Fig. 2 The dynamics of the volume of emissions by activity sectors in Balti municipality (2014 - 2021)

For the period 2014 - 2018, the largest volumes, about 70%, were emitted by the energy sector, and the rest from the industrial sector (Fig. 2). Starting with 2019, the industrial sector emits about 700 tons of emissions into the atmosphere compared to about 300 tons by 2018. Among the largest companies in the thermal energy sector with increased emission volumes is J.S.C. "CET-Nord" with 50.29 t in 2021 and Î.M. „Termogaz Bălți” with 9.102 t. Regarding the transport services sector, there is an increase in the volume of emissions from 151.107 t in 2019 to 170.819 t in 2021. Among the biggest polluters in this field are LTD "Lukoil Moldova" - 36,069 t considering all the fuel supply points from the municipality, followed by LTD „Dominic” – 34.441 t., LTD „Petroim Moldova” – 29.382 t., LTD „Bemol Retail” - 12, 563 t., etc. In the food production sector for 2021 stand out J.S.C.. „Floarea Soarelui” with 604.287 t., J.S.C. "Incomlac" – 29.548 t., J.S.C.. "Vinăria din Vale" - 7,449 t., J.S.C.. "Basarabia Nord" - 6,008 t. The sector of production of construction materials in the Balti municipality is represented by Î.M. MG „CMC-Knauf” with 26.953 t., LTD „Dolomita Prim” (with the specificity of producing concrete articles) with 6.673 t. and others with a lower volume. An increased volume of emissions for the Balti urban ecosystem is also represented by LTD "Gloring Engineering", which in the process of activity for 2021 emitted into the atmosphere 241.863 t. The composition of the emissions of this economic agent is 69% hydrocarbons (CH), followed by CO - 21% and solids - 3%. Nitrogen and sulphur dioxide (NO₂ and SO₂) accounted for 1% each.

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Key words: air pollution, biggest polluters, economic agents, urban ecosystem, volume of emissions.

EUROPIUM BIOACCUMULATION BY *ARTROSPIRA PLATENSIS* AND ITS EFFECT ON BIOMASS

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Europium is one of the most reactive rare-earth elements, which due to its physical and chemical properties is widely applied in many technological processes. Nowadays, it is imperative to develop sustainable, eco-friendly and promising extraction techniques and explore alternative europium resources, along with protecting the environment and human health. The ability of cyanobacteria, *Artrospira platensis*, to accumulate europium and its effect on biomass biochemical composition was evaluated. Europium accumulation in biomass was traced by ICP-AES technique. At addition of europium ions in the cultivation medium in concentrations 10-30 mg/L, its accumulation in biomass was 9.8-29.8 mg/g (removal efficiency being) 98-99%. Europium ions in studied concentrations range did not affect productivity and content of carbohydrates and pigments in biomass, and led to the decrease of the content of protein and an increase in the amount of MDA. *Artrospira platensis* can be considered as a potential bioremediator for treatment of wastewater polluted with europium.

Key words: *Artrospira platensis*, alternative europium resources, bioremediator, biomass, extraction techniques.

FINDING OF THE REMAINS OF A FROG AND VARAN FROM THE PLIOCENE LOCALITY PRIOZERNOE

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During the 2021 season fieldwork, reptile and amphibian remains were found in the early Pliocene alluvial sediments of the Dniester River valley in a sandstone quarry near the village of Priozernoie (Moldova, Transdnistria).

The reptile remains, represented by a vertebra of the trunk, belonged to a large lizard, identified by us as *Varanus* sp. From the Pliocene deposits of Moldavia, there is only an indication of the presence of *Varanus* sp. from the localities Etulia and Suvorovo (Zerova & Chkhikvadze, 1984) (description and photos are not provided), which requires clarification. The closest Pliocene faunal localities from which remains of a representative of this family have been previously described are located in the Odessa Region, Ukraine (Kotlovina-1 and Kotlovina-2) (Ratnikov, 2002).

At the end of the field season, a torso vertebra of a large amphibian of the order Anura was found. The vertebra is very large, more than 2 cm wide. It belonged to a frog of the family Palaeobatrachidae. The *Palaeobatrachus* cf. *langhae* (biozones MN 14-15) was a characteristic species of the Pliocene of Europe (Hungary, Poland, Russia and Slovakia) (Ratnikov, 1997, 2002; Villa, Roček et al., 2016). The remains have been tentatively identified as *Palaeobatrachus* sp. Thus, for the first time for the Pliocene of the Republic of Moldova (Transdnistria) a new species of large frog of the family Palaeobatrachidae was identified. The presence of lizards of the family Varanidae in the Pliocene in the Dniester River valley was also reliably established.

These findings supplement our understanding of the fauna of our region during the Early Pliocene and allow us to clarify the paleogeographic and paleoecological conditions of the early stages of formation of the large paleo-river valleys of the Dniester and Prut rivers.

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References:

Ratnikov V.Yu. On the finds of Pliobatrachus (Anura, Palaeobatrachidae) in Eastern Europe / Paleontological Journal, № 4, 1997. 70-76 pp.

Ratnikov V.Yu. Late Cenozoic amphibians and squamate reptiles of the East-European Platform / Trudy Nauchno-Issledovatel'skogo Instituta Geologii Voronezhskogo Universiteta, Voronezh, 10. 2002. P. 138.

Villa A., Roček Z., Tschopp E., van den Hoek Ostende L.W., and Delfino M. *Palaeobatrachus eurydices*, sp. nov. (Amphibia, Anura), the last western European palaeobatrachid / Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology, 36(6), 2016. 415-421 pp.

Zerova G.A. & Chkhikvadze V.M. Review of Cenozoic lizards and snakes of the USSR / Izvestia of the Academy of Sciences of the Georgian SSR. Ser. Biology, vol. 10, № 5, 1984. 319-326 pp.

Keywords: *Palaeobatrachus* cf. *langhae*, paleoecological conditions, reptile remains, Pliocene deposits,